

26/02/2026

Version 1.0

BMD

Biodiversity Meets Data

MS11 Legislative species checklist mobilised to Catalogue of Life ChecklistBank

Author(s): [Camila Plata \(COL\)](#) & [Olaf Bánki \(COL\)](#)

Contributor(s): [Diana Hernández \(COL\)](#), [Donald Hobern \(COL\)](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

BMD (Biodiversity Meets Data) receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) (ID No 101181294). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Research Executive Agency (REA) or SERI. The EU, REA and SERI cannot be held responsible for them.

Prepared under contract from the European Commission

Grant agreement No. 101181294

EU Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action

Project acronym:	BMD
Project full title:	Biodiversity Meets Data
Project duration:	01.03.2025 – 28.02.2029 (48 months)
Project coordinator:	Stichting Naturalis Biodiversity Center (Naturalis)
Call:	HORIZON-CL6-2024-BIODIV-01
Milestone title:	M11 Legislative species checklist mobilised to Catalogue of Life ChecklistBank
Milestone n°:	M11
Means of verification:	Species checklists incorporated into COL ChecklistBank
Work package:	WP2
Nature of the milestone:	Report, Data
Contribution to deliverable n°:	D2.2.b.2027, month 24
Licence of use:	CC0
Lead beneficiary:	Stichting Catalogue of Life (Catalogue of Life)
Recommended citation:	Plata, C., Bánki, O., Hernández, D., Hobern, D. (2026). Legislative species checklist mobilised to Catalogue of Life ChecklistBank. BMD project deliverable M11
Due date of milestone:	28 February 2026 (M12)
Actual submission date:	28 February 2026
Quality review:	Yes

Milestone status:

Version	Status	Date	Author(s)	Actions
0.1	1st Draft	31 January 2026	Camila Plata, Olaf Bánki, Diana Hernández, Donald Hobern, Catalogue of Life Foundation	Sent for review
0.2		17 February 2026	Mette Palitzsch Lund, Claus Weiland, Mathias Dillen, Chiara Bortoluzzi	Reviewed

0.3	2nd Draft	25 February 2026	Camila Plata, Olaf Bánki, Catalogue of Life Foundation	Finalised, with incorporation of feedback from reviewers
1.0	Final	26 February 2026	Camila Plata, Olaf Bánki, Diana Hernández, Donald Hobern, Catalogue of Life Foundation	Submitted

Table of contents

Table of contents	4
Summary	6
List of abbreviations	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1 The Catalogue of Life	9
1.1.1 Catalogue of Life infrastructure: ChecklistBank	10
1.1.2 Catalogue of Life's role in Biodiversity Meets Data	10
1.1.2.1 Biodiversity Meets Data, subtask 2.1.2 (in WP2)	10
1.1.2.2 Biodiversity Meets Data, subtask 2.2.2 (in WP2)	10
1.2 Policy-relevant Species Lists	11
1.2.1 The European Environment Agency (EEA)	12
1.2.2 EU Habitats Directive	12
2. Mobilization of policy-relevant species lists	13
2.1 Current state of the EU Habitats Directive Lists	14
2.3 Methodology	14
2.3.1 ChecklistBank Data Assessment - subtask 2.1.2 (in WP2)	14
2.3.2 Mobilising policy relevant species checklists - subtask 2.2.2 (in WP2)	15
2.3.2.1 Requirements Assessment	15
2.3.2.2 Extraction Protocol	16
Interpretation manual	16
Legal Annexes II, IV, V	18
2.3.2.3 Data Publishing	18
2.4 ChecklistBank Data Assessment results - subtask 2.1.2 (in WP2)	19
2.4.1 Invasive species-related checklists	19
2.4.2 National-related checklists	20
2.5 Mobilising policy relevant species checklists results - subtask 2.2.2 (in WP2)	23
2.5.1 Interpretation Manual of European Union habitats Raw list (Annex 1)	23
2.5.1 Habitats Directive, Legal Annexes II, IV, V	24
3. Further work	25
4. Acknowledgements	25
5. References	25
6. Annexes	27
Annex 1	27
Operational Definition	27
1. Scope of Extraction	27
2. What Qualifies as a Valid Scientific Name	27
3. Explicit Exclusions	28

3.1 Syntaxonomic Units (ALWAYS EXCLUDED)	28
3.2 Structural / Editorial Elements (EXCLUDED)	28
4. Handling of Abbreviations	28
4.1 Abbreviated Genera	28
4.2 "spp." Rule	28
5. Intraspecific Names	29
5.1 Embedded in scientificName	29
5.2 Rank Column Values	29
5.3 Normalization	29
6. No Taxonomic Interpretation	29
7. No Deduplication Unless Requested	29
8. Output Format	30
Field Definitions	30
9. Inclusion Logic Summary	30
Annex 2	31
Annex 3	57

Summary

In the Biodiversity Meets Data project, Catalogue of Life serves as the taxonomic reference for the biodiversity data used. The Catalogue of Life infrastructure, ChecklistBank, serves as a repository ('data catalogue') for taxonomic, nomenclatural, and other species list data sources, like national or policy relevant and legal species lists.

In this milestone report, work by Catalogue of Life is reported for two tasks. For task 2.1.2, an overview is provided of the relevant invasive species lists and national species list already mediated through Catalogue of Life's ChecklistBank. For task 2.2.2b, work is reported on the mobilisation and publishing of the EU Directives open species data in Catalogue of Life's ChecklistBank.

Catalogue of Life ChecklistBank mediates (partial) national species lists originating from 26 of the 27 European Union Member States. Several countries have multiple lists that can be considered as partial national lists, and that are not merged into one national species reference list. There are 52 invasive species lists published from Europe as open data in ChecklistBank. Again, some countries publish multiple invasive species lists, and not necessarily one unified list for the entire country. The corpus of available open species data originating from national and/or invasive species lists in Catalogue of Life's ChecklistBank is already very high. These data are available for use in the Biodiversity Meets Data project, and free to use for Natura 2000 site managers.

Policy-relevant species lists are fundamental instruments for biodiversity management, defining which taxa are subject to legal protection, monitoring, reporting, or management under international, regional, and national frameworks. Unlike purely scientific taxonomic lists, these datasets establish binding obligations and therefore require high levels of transparency, traceability to legal sources, and long-term stability, while remaining interoperable with evolving taxonomic knowledge.

Within the European Union, the European Environment Agency (EEA) coordinates biodiversity data reported by Member States, supported by the European Nature Information System (EUNIS). The Catalogue of Life (COL) has served as the taxonomic reference for EUNIS since 2016.

Building on a long-standing collaboration, the EEA and the Catalogue of Life agreed, within the framework of the Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) project, to develop a roadmap for the publication and harmonisation of species data from EU Directives. A *de novo*, machine-readable extraction of scientific names from the Habitats Directive was undertaken to establish a transparent baseline directly traceable to the legal texts and associated interpretation manuals. Previous mobilisation attempts could not be reused due to missing metadata and unclear links to original sources.

For Annex I, which lists 233 habitat types of community interest, scientific names were extracted from the Interpretation Manual of European Union Habitats (2013) using a controlled protocol combining artificial intelligence (ChatGPT-5.2) with expert review. The AI was guided by a structured prompt designed to preserve only explicitly stated scientific names without taxonomic normalisation or revision. For Annexes II, IV, and V, which follow a straightforward list format, extraction primarily involved mapping entries into the Catalogue of Life Data Package (ColDP) standard using Excel, OpenRefine, and

ChecklistBank data quality flags. Informal, non-monophyletic group names (e.g., "Invertebrates," "Fishes") were removed to improve navigation.

The resulting raw datasets have been published in ChecklistBank under a CC0 licence. The Annex I dataset contains 4,366 records representing 3,110 unique scientific names associated with 228 of the 233 habitat types. Taxonomic composition is dominated by Plantae (94.2%). The Annex II, IV, and V datasets contain 1,068, 1,127, and 149 names respectively.

These datasets preserve scientific names exactly as they appear in the Directive, including typographical errors. They are intended primarily as a legal reference. For scientific purposes, a second version will be developed with taxonomic harmonisation to the Catalogue of Life.

The methodology will be extended to the Birds Directive and the Invasive Alien Species Regulation, ensuring coherence across EU nature conservation legislation.

List of abbreviations

BMD	Biodiversity Meets Data
EU	European Union
COL	Catalogue of Life
EEA	European Environment Agency
EUNIS	European Nature Information System
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
SAP	Single Access Point
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package
CITES	Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES)
CMS	Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
GRIIS	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species
CoIDP	Catalogue of Life Data Package
ISSG	Invasive Species Specialist Group

1. Introduction

1.1 The Catalogue of Life

Catalogue of Life's mission is a world where biodiversity data is connected, harmonized and accessible, enabling our understanding and preservation of life on Earth. Its mission is to forge a global community that manages an authoritative catalogue of species, through an infrastructure that supports open data publishing and use. The Catalogue of Life (COL) is an international collaboration that brings together the efforts and contributions of taxonomists and informaticians from around the world. Its objective is to meet the needs of researchers, policymakers, environmental managers, and the wider public by providing a consistent and up-to-date listing of all known species and their higher taxa. The Catalogue of Life represents a consensus classification (Bánki et al. 2026), based on underlying taxonomic source databases and managed by a global community of more than 500 experts (Costello et al. 2022).

As the most comprehensive initiative to compile a single, integrated list of the world's known species, the Catalogue of Life relies on a global network of specialists to ensure accuracy, completeness, and taxonomic consistency. By translating expert taxonomic knowledge into a reference that is simple to use and understand, COL supports scientific research, policy development, biodiversity management, and public access to authoritative taxonomic information. It also provides a reliable backbone for users who manage their own taxonomic data and species lists.

The Catalogue of Life is distributed through releases that reflect different levels of coverage and quality: the Base Release and the eXtended Release¹. These releases are updated throughout the year and published in both monthly and annual versions.

The Catalogue of Life Base Release is an assembly of non-overlapping, expert-curated global species checklists, organized according to the Catalogue's management classification. Its construction ensures a high level of quality, as most contributing data sources are regularly maintained and updated by taxonomic experts. However, because many taxa still lack a vetted or up-to-date global checklist, this approach leaves gaps in coverage. To address these gaps, the Catalogue of Life eXtended Release is built on top of the Base Release. In this process, the Base Release is programmatically enhanced through the integration of information from more than 20,000 overlapping taxonomic and nomenclatural sources, including global, regional, national, and management datasets, as well as digitized literature. This process enriches existing names with additional information such as authorships, references, vernacular names, and, where available, molecular data (e.g. barcode index numbers or operational taxonomic units). Higher-level classification (from subphyla and below) is also added for selected groups with significant gaps such as invertebrates and algae, while the information originating from the Base Release remains unmodified. The enhancement workflow is continuously evolving and subject to quality control by COL editors and the broader expert community.

The Catalogue of Life is now integrating global, regional, and national data sources through its eXtended Release. It has become suited to organizing the 3.6 billion species occurrences mediated through GBIF. The Catalogue of Life Foundation now serves as the GBIF Associate Participant that is focused on

¹ <https://www.catalogueoflife.org/building/releases>

supplying taxonomic data services and support for the open data publishing of taxonomic, nomenclatural, and species lists (including national and policy relevant lists). Catalogue of Life as taxonomic reference for GBIF enables monthly updates, incorporation of overlapping taxon sources including molecular data, and improved attribution through authorship and vernacular names, capabilities that directly address the limitations of the previous GBIF Backbone Taxonomy. Currently GBIF is transitioning to use COL as its main global taxonomic reference in its main website gbif.org and through its species API, offering the authoritative, continuously harmonized foundation essential for tracking biodiversity

1.1.1 Catalogue of Life infrastructure: ChecklistBank

ChecklistBank (checklistbank.org) is the Catalogue of Life infrastructure that supports the publication, analysis, and curation of datasets with an emphasis on taxonomic and nomenclatural data. It hosts all data sources that contribute to the Catalogue of Life data product, which are primarily global species lists provided by specific taxonomic communities. Beyond its role in building the Catalogue, ChecklistBank supports a wide range of other types of checklists, such as national and regional species lists, policy-relevant datasets like the IUCN Red or invasive species lists, and compilations derived from taxonomic publications. Through ChecklistBank, we facilitate the discovery, use and citation of these valuable resources.

ChecklistBank plays a fundamental role in ensuring that basic data on species names and classifications can be shared and reused to support biological research and wider societal uses. It has been developed and maintained by the Catalogue of Life (COL) and in close collaboration with the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

1.1.2 Catalogue of Life's role in Biodiversity Meets Data

Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) is a European Commission funded project geared towards establishing a Single Access Point (SAP) to high-throughput biodiversity monitoring tools, biodiversity data, and biodiversity analyses for better conservation across Europe. Catalogue of Life's role in the project is to provide the taxonomic reference data service. Its involvement is in the workpackages 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, and 8.

1.1.2.1 Biodiversity Meets Data, subtask 2.1.2 (in WP2)

Catalogue of Life through its infrastructure ChecklistBank, is to support the cataloguing of taxonomic legislative, and other species-related list data sources. This includes national species lists whether mandated by the national governments or originating out of the scientific community. The process will be guided by the specific criteria and policies these registries have for dataset inclusion. ChecklistBank is a key external resource to validate and enhance the taxonomic quality and relevance of the datasets being catalogued within the BMD project's GeoNetwork system.

1.1.2.2 Biodiversity Meets Data, subtask 2.2.2 (in WP2)

Catalogue of Life aims to mobilise policy relevant data to ChecklistBank, such that these data sets can be taxonomically harmonised with the Catalogue of Life in Work Package 3. This harmonisation will enable data cubing of species occurrences and eventually will drive particular usage in Virtual Research

Environments (VRE) developed in Work Package 5. The main focus of this milestone is to showcase how lists of species relevant to the European Union, such as the lists of the annexes of the Birds and Habitats Directive and the Invasive Alien Species Regulation, can be mobilised to the Catalogue of Life ChecklistBank infrastructure.

1.2 Policy-relevant Species Lists

Policy-relevant species lists are authoritative compilations of taxa that are formally recognised within legal, regulatory, or policy frameworks at international, regional, or national levels. These lists are produced or endorsed by multilateral agreements, regional directives, or national legislation, and they define which species are subject to obligations such as protection, monitoring, trade regulation, restoration measures, or management controls. Well-known global examples include the appendices of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES)², the species listings under the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS)³, and the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species⁴. At the regional level, prominent examples include the annexes of the European Union's Habitats and Birds Directives and the Bern Convention lists for European wildlife among others. At national or subnational levels, countries maintain legally binding protected species lists, national Red Lists, invasive alien species lists, and priority species catalogues that directly inform the issuing of permits for developments, land-use planning, environmental impact assessments, biodiversity monitoring, protected area establishment and management, amongst others.

Unlike purely taxonomic checklists, policy-relevant lists determine which taxa must be monitored, reported on, regulated, or prioritised for conservation action. They drive the structure of monitoring programmes, shape reporting obligations under international agreements and regional directives, and influence the design of biodiversity databases and information flows. For example, EU reporting under the Habitats and Birds Directives is explicitly tied to fixed annex lists, while global indicators under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Sustainable Development Goals rely on species included in the IUCN Red List and other recognised policy frameworks.

As part of its strategic plan, the Catalogue of Life supports the publication and harmonisation of policy-relevant species lists. This work will define clear workflows and standards to enable interoperable publication, improve traceability between legal instruments and taxonomic data, and reduce duplication of efforts across institutions, supporting more consistent use of these lists in biodiversity reporting and policy processes. The Catalogue of Life infrastructure, ChecklistBank, already hosts policy-relevant species lists, including the IUCN Red List, more than 200 invasive species lists such as those from the Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species (GRIIS), and a range of national legislative lists. In parallel, the Catalogue of Life has actively engaged with several institutions that produce and maintain such lists to establish different kinds of partnerships; these efforts are described in Biodiversity Meets Data Work Package 1. Together, these datasets and collaborations form a baseline for further harmonisation and standardisation within the Catalogue of Life.

² [cites.org](https://www.cites.org)

³ www.cms.int

⁴ www.iucnredlist.org

1.2.1 The European Environment Agency (EEA)

The European Environment Agency (EEA) supports environmental policymaking by providing independent, reliable, and comparable environmental information. The EEA works in close partnership with EU Member States and cooperating countries to collect, harmonise, analyse, and disseminate environmental data. Its mandate covers a wide range of thematic areas, including biodiversity, ecosystems, climate change, land use, water, and pollution, and it plays a central role in coordinating and supporting environmental monitoring and reporting under EU legislation such as the Habitats and Birds Directives. By translating data into assessments, indicators, and knowledge products, the EEA enables evidence-based decision-making and supports the implementation, evaluation, and communication of EU environmental policies.

The European Nature Information System (EUNIS)⁵ brings together data from several reporting streams and data products into three interlinked modules on European sites, species and habitat types. The EUNIS information system is being integrated within the Biodiversity Information System for Europe (BISE) which is a contribution to the knowledge base for implementing the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. EUNIS and its underlying database is a reference for European habitat types and the visualisation of protected species of the Natura 2000 network (EU Birds and Habitats Directives) and the related Emerald Network of the Bern Convention. Catalogue of Life is the taxonomic reference for EUNIS since 2016. It is used within EUNIS as a primary taxonomic reference to ensure consistent species naming and classification which enables cross-dataset interoperability across EEA biodiversity products.

Within the Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) project, the species lists related to the Birds and Habitats Directives and the Invasive Alien Species Regulation will be mobilised. During the first phase of the process, priority was given to the Habitats Directive Annexes containing scientific names. The extraction methodology is documented in this report.

1.2.2 EU Habitats Directive

The EU Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) is a central instrument of European nature conservation policy, aiming to achieve and maintain the favourable conservation status of selected habitats and species of community interest across the European Union. While the Directive is adopted and enforced at EU level, the European Environment Agency (EEA) plays a key role in its implementation by coordinating, harmonising, and synthesising biodiversity data reported by Member States. In particular, the EEA supports the data collection for Natura 2000 network and the reporting under Article 17, develops assessment methodologies and indicators, and produces EU-wide analyses, including the State of Nature reports, thereby enabling consistent and policy-relevant assessments at the European scale.

The policy scope of the Habitats Directive is defined through Annex I, which lists approximately 230 among terrestrial and marine habitat types, each identified by a stable code used across EU reporting systems. Member States submit annually a database with Natura 2000 sites designated for the protection of the habitat types and report on these habitats every six years under Article 17, using

⁵ <https://biodiversity.europa.eu/>

quantitative parameters such as range, area, structure and functions, trends, and pressures. The most recent completed reporting cycle covered 2013–2018, with EU-level results published in 2020, while the current cycle covers 2019–2024. In this context, the Annex I habitat list serves both as a legal reference and as a structured data framework enabling repeatable and comparable habitat assessments over time.

To support consistent application of these legally defined habitat types, the Interpretation Manual of European Union Habitats⁶ provides operational scientific descriptions, clarifying the scope, diagnostic features, and regional variation of each Annex I habitat. While not legally binding, the manual plays a key role in harmonizing interpretation across Member States and resolving ambiguities arising from the abstract nature of the Annex I definitions.

A similar structure applies to the species protected under the Habitat Directive, which are distributed across Annexes II, IV, and V. Annex II lists species whose conservation requires the designation of Special Areas of Conservation. Annex IV lists species in need of strict protection across the EU, while Annex V covers species that may be subject to management measures if taken from the wild. However, as with habitats, these legal annexes are not used directly for reporting, but are an integral part of the directive thus legally binding. They are transposed into species reference lists and species checklists and revised every six years. This provides the operational basis for Member State reporting under Article 17 and for the Natura 2000 network. These lists used for reporting also account for endemic species that require particular attention due to their habitat specificity or the potential impact of their exploitation.

2. Mobilization of policy-relevant species lists

Policy-relevant species lists are often taxonomically static or updated infrequently, whereas scientific taxonomy evolves continuously. As a result, species names embedded in legal and policy instruments may become synonyms, be split or merged, or change taxonomic rank over time. The associated legal obligations remain tied to the original names, as seen in long-standing frameworks such as the EU Habitats Directive. In addition, these lists introduce substantial temporal, geographic, and legal complexity, since the same species may have different statuses across jurisdictions, be regulated under multiple instruments, or change status through amendments and periodic assessment cycles. Such differences are evident, for example, between global threat assessments under the IUCN Red List and regional or national Red Lists, or between international trade controls under CITES and national protection measures. In this context, name-resolution services and taxonomic reference lists, such as the Catalogue of Life, are essential for linking legislative names to current taxonomic usage while preserving legal meaning, historical context, and traceability.

The Catalogue of Life wants to provide adequate mechanisms to support versioning, provenance, scope, and jurisdiction, ensuring that species data are correctly interpreted within their relevant policy context. Through ChecklistBank, interoperability is enabled between taxonomic references, occurrence data, threat assessments, monitoring results, and legal instruments. This integration helps ensure that

⁶<https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/3f466d71-92a7-49eb-9c63-6cb0fadf29dc/library/37d9e6d9-b7de-42ce-b789-622e9741b68f/details>

policy-relevant species lists remain usable, consistent, and scientifically grounded, thereby supporting evidence-based conservation policy and effective biodiversity governance across scales. Although not legally binding themselves, ChecklistBank also hosts a wide array of policy-relevant species lists, many of which originate from academic research and serve as foundational resources. Within the scope of this project is also worth having a better understanding of the list already available.

In this report we focus on the publishing process of the EEA policy-relevant species lists and particularly on the EU Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) Annexes.

2.1 Current state of the EU Habitats Directive Lists

Despite the central role of the EU Habitats Directive in biodiversity management across Europe, there is currently no official, open data interoperable version of its original species lists published by the European Commission DG Environment and the European Environment Agency (EEA). In practice, available lists are not direct representations of the legally adopted annexes, but scientific interpretations derived from the legal text and from the Interpretation Manual of the European Union Habitats. Consequently, it remains difficult to clearly identify and reference the actual legal lists as open data, and similar data-processing efforts are repeatedly undertaken by institutions across Europe, leading to duplication, inconsistencies, and inefficiencies.

For Annex I, this situation is exacerbated by the format of the EU Directive and Interpretation Manual, which is primarily available as PDF documents in which scientific names are dispersed across descriptive texts and lists, making reliable data extraction difficult. While about 32 EEA-related checklists are available through ChecklistBank, they lack sufficient metadata and clear links to the originating legal instruments. A collaboration between the EEA, DG Environment and the Catalogue of Life, within the BMD project, wants to address this gap. A *de novo*, EEA-endorsed, machine-readable extraction of the characteristic species of Habitats Directive Annexes was produced.

For all annexes two versions are going to be produced: a raw version, which preserves the original spellings and nomenclature used in the Habitats Directive in order to retain the full information content of the legal document, and an interpreted version, which will undergo data quality checks to correct misspellings and harmonise the taxonomic information with the latest version of the Catalogue of Life, as referred on Work Package 3 Milestone 17. The section below describes the process and results related to the raw versions of the lists.

2.3 Methodology

2.3.1 ChecklistBank Data Assessment - subtask 2.1.2 (in WP2)

Although the Catalogue of Life is primarily built from globally vetted taxonomic sources, its infrastructure—ChecklistBank—hosts more than 64,000 species lists published by multiple institutions

and countries, covering a wide range of biodiversity topics. These include policy-relevant species lists and nationally legally and non-binding species lists. In Biodiversity Meets Data, ChecklistBank is serving as the registry and catalogue for these data types.

To better understand the existing material already available on ChecklistBank, much of which originates from diverse academic efforts, research networks, and national initiatives, an assessment was carried out to review the volume and scope of lists related to invasive species, Red List assessments, and national legislative lists, with a particular focus on the Europe. This scoping exercise aims to map what is currently accessible, identify taxonomic and geographic coverage patterns, and evaluate the potential for reusing and integrating these lists into coherent, policy-ready data products. By examining the landscape of existing checklists, the assessment provides a foundational overview that can inform subsequent harmonization efforts and support the alignment of scientific and policy nomenclature. This is an activity, contributing to BMD Task 2.1.

2.3.2 Mobilising policy relevant species checklists - subtask 2.2.2 (in WP2)

2.3.2.1 Requirements Assessment

The needs of the European Environment Agency (EEA) were jointly assessed through a series of coordination meetings between the EEA and the Catalogue of Life (COL) teams. These discussions focused on defining a roadmap for the publication of species data associated with the Habitats and Birds Directives, as well as other policy-relevant species lists managed by the Agency.

Collaboration between COL and the EEA has been ongoing since 2016, when the Catalogue of Life began serving as the taxonomic data service for the EUNIS system. This long-standing cooperation provided the background for the planned activities in the BMD project. Activities carried out during the BMD project period, starting on 1 March 2025, are considered part of the BMD work. Further details on the strategic context of these discussions and the topics addressed are presented in Work Package 1.

As part of this process, existing information in ChecklistBank originating from a previous EEA mobilisation attempt lead by Belgian Biodiversity Platform was reviewed⁷. However, according to the EEA the available information refers to the reported species by the Member States during the six-year-reporting cycle, not to the original uninterpreted information of the Habitats Directive. Additionally, due to incomplete metadata and insufficient documentation, a clear and verifiable link to the original legal sources could not be established, in a detailed revision several species names included couldn't be traced back to the Interpretation Manual. Therefore, the dataset was considered not suitable for reuse as a raw datasource. Previous species extractions commissioned by the EEA to the European Topic Center on Biological Diversity (ETC/BD) were also evaluated (work ended in 2022). While these provided useful approximations, they did not document how scientific interpretation had been applied, making it impossible to determine which elements were directly derived from the legal texts and which resulted from subsequent interpretative decisions; these are also very likely to be part of the six-year-reporting cycle. Consequently, the EEA and the Catalogue of Life agreed to carry out a *de novo* extraction, starting

⁷ <https://www.checklistbank.org/dataset/207733/metadata>

with the Habitats Directive. The *de novo* extraction was designed to capture the content of the Habitats Directive exactly as published in the legal texts and the associated Interpretation Manual. This should provide a transparent baseline for subsequent scientific name interpretation, harmonisation, and taxonomic alignment.

2.3.2.2 Extraction Protocol

Interpretation manual

The extraction of scientific names from the Interpretation Manual⁸ replete to the Habitats Directive Annex I was supported by using artificial intelligence, specifically ChatGPT-5.2, guided by a structured and constrained prompt.

Initial tests were conducted to assess the accuracy and performance of the AI, and to develop a prompt capable of producing the desired results. These tests involved extracting scientific names from three types of input: copied and pasted text, a PDF, and a Word document. The results were reviewed and compared against the original information, and any extraction errors were used to iteratively refine the prompt. The texts varied in structure and complexity, including abbreviations, infraspecific names, synonyms, and habitat descriptions to capture the complexity of the Interpretation Manual (Fig 1.).

⁸<https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/3f466d71-92a7-49eb-9c63-6cb0fadf29dc/library/37d9e6d9-b7de-42ce-b789-622e9741b68f/details>

Figure 1. Overview of page 7 of the Interpretation Manual - EUR28 showing the complexity of the text, and presence of scientific names across sections of the habitat's description.

It was observed that ChatGPT performs poorly when processing very large text blocks (e.g., more than 5 pages), particularly from PDFs and Word documents, although its performance was better with the latter. In such cases, the model often simplifies tasks or relaxes the given rules, leading to incomplete extractions. To address this, the source material was divided into smaller text segments (in Word documents) with no more than 10 habitats at a time, and categorized into three sections based on the Interpretation Manual: 1) descriptions, narrative text of the habitat containing embedded scientific names; 2) characteristic animal and plant species, primarily scientific names grouped by kingdom; and 3)

corresponding categories, covering subtypes, regional varieties, and correspondences with other classification systems, often syntactically dense but containing few or no scientific names. Additionally, kingdom misassignments were frequent, so a secondary extraction focused solely on animals was carried out to ensure completeness.

Based on the tests, a final prompt ([Annex I](#)) was built, and stored in the chat memory. It instructed the model to extract only explicitly stated scientific taxon names, prioritizing typographic cues, and to avoid inferring or normalizing names beyond what appeared in the source text.

Specific rules addressed taxonomic edge cases, including retention of infraspecific names, reduction of Genus spp. entries to genus level, and expansion of abbreviated genera (e.g., E. species) only when unambiguous within the same text. Narrative, ecological, geographic, and procedural phrases were excluded, as were entries containing digits and footnote markers.

Independent habitat-by-habitat extractions were also performed for habitats with long and complex text segments, this was made directly pasting the texts into the chat to introduce redundancy and reduce the likelihood of missing species names; the information was later deduplicated by a reviewer (a COL editor) using OpenRefine.

The extraction process was continuously monitored and cross-checked by a human reviewer (a COL editor), with a previous extraction done by EEA's ETC/BD used as an independent reference. When missing species were identified during the first quality review, a full re-extraction of the corresponding habitat text was conducted.

Following extraction, a second data quality review (by a COL editor) focused on resolving duplicates, identifying missing or inconsistent taxonomic ranks, verifying habitat codes and titles, and removing residual qualifiers or non-scientific descriptive text.

Legal Annexes II, IV, V

In contrast to the Interpretation Manual, Annexes II, IV, and V of the Habitats Directive followed a straightforward list format. The data extraction therefore primarily involved mapping the listed entries into the ColDP standard. All original scientific names were preserved as they appear in the Directive, while informal, non-monophyletic group names such as "Invertebrates" and "Fishes", were removed to improve navigation of the checklist. This process was carried out using Excel, OpenRefine, and the data quality flags available in ChecklistBank.

2.3.2.3 Data Publishing

The data were standardised using the Catalogue of Life Data Package (ColDP, <https://catalogueoflife.github.io/coldp/>). Given the raw nature of the list only the kingdom is provided as a higher classification, as this is the only hierarchical level specified in the Interpretation Manual. Rank and status are included, and habitat IDs and names are stored as atomized taxon properties.

This first raw dataset of the Habitats Directive has been published in ChecklistBank under a CC0 licence⁹. The final publisher of the dataset is still to be defined by the EEA, DG Environment and the European Commission.

2.4 ChecklistBank Data Assessment results - subtask 2.1.2 (in WP2)

2.4.1 Invasive species–related checklists

An assessment of invasive species–related checklists currently available in ChecklistBank identified 420 published checklists ([Annex 3](#)). Of these, 305 (73%) were published by the Invasive Species Specialist Group (ISSG). However, a substantial proportion of these ISSG lists have not been updated in over three years.

A further 80 checklists are mediated by Plazi (<https://plazi.org/>) and originate from peer-reviewed journal publications. The remaining lists are provided by a range of research organisations and governmental institutions, reflecting diverse publication pathways and update cycles across the invasive species domain.

Regional coverage is uneven. Sub-Saharan Africa (100 checklists) and Latin America and the Caribbean (58) are the most represented regions, followed by Micronesia (31) and Southern Europe (33). Other European and Asian regions show moderate to low coverage, while Northern America (5), Melanesia (2), and several other regions remain sparsely represented (Table 1). Within Europe, Spain leads with 9 invasive species checklists, followed by Belgium with 8.

Table 1: Number of invasive, exotic or alien related species checklists available through ChecklistBank by January 2026

Region	# of checklists
Sub-Saharan Africa	100
Latin America and the Caribbean	58
Southern Europe	33
Micronesia	31
Western Europe	19
Polynesia	17
Western Asia	15

⁹ <https://www.checklistbank.org/dataset/313964>

Northern Europe	12
Southern Asia	11
Eastern Asia	10
Eastern Europe	8
Northern Africa	7
South-eastern Asia	7
Central Asia	6
Northern America	5
Australia and New Zealand	4
Melanesia	2
Europe (generic)	2
Unassigned	73

2.4.2 National-related checklists

An assessment of the national-related checklists currently available in ChecklistBank identified 1,005 published checklists. Of these, 865 (86%) were published via Plazi which mobilises multiple biodiversity related journals. The remaining 140 species lists were published by country related institutions like universities, research institutes and governmental entities. The CC0 license is the most predominant among the national lists being used in 773 (77%) of the cases, followed by a similar number of lists under CC-BY (117, 12%) and CC-BY-NC (115, 11%) licenses. These lists represent the biodiversity of 151 countries, with China, Poland and Brazil having 100, 99 and 70 national lists respectively. Those, influencing the regional distribution of national checklists, with Latin America and the Caribbean (167), Eastern Europe (137), and Eastern Asia (107) being the most represented regions (Table 2). These trends ultimately mirror the publication trends of biodiversity where China and Brazil are leaders. The high representation of Eastern Europe is driven by a publication structure of checklists by chapters by the Polish Biodiversity Information Network. The European region has checklists representing 37 out of the 52 countries for 71% coverage of the region, 26 of these countries are EU Member states (Table 3).

Table 2: Number of national-related checklists available through ChecklistBank by January 2026

Sub-Region	# of checklists
Latin America and the Caribbean	167
Eastern Europe	137
Eastern Asia	133
Sub-Saharan Africa	114
Southern Asia	103
South-eastern Asia	92
Western Asia	69
Southern Europe	61
Western Europe	34
Northern Europe	25
Melanesia	18
Northern Africa	18
Northern America	18
Australia and New Zealand	16
Central Asia	4
Unclassified	4
Antarctica	3
Micronesia	1

Table 3: Detail of the European countries publishing national-related checklists available through ChecklistBank by January 2026.

Country	Subregion	EU Member	Country	Subregion	EU Member
Belarus	Eastern Europe	No	Albania	Southern Europe	No
Bulgaria	Eastern Europe	Yes	Croatia	Southern Europe	Yes
Czech Republic	Eastern Europe	Yes	Greece	Southern Europe	Yes
Hungary	Eastern Europe	Yes	Italy	Southern Europe	Yes
Poland	Eastern Europe	Yes	Malta	Southern Europe	Yes
Romania	Eastern Europe	Yes	Montenegro	Southern Europe	No
Russia	Eastern Europe	No	North Macedonia	Southern Europe	No
Slovakia	Eastern Europe	Yes	Portugal	Southern Europe	Yes
Ukraine	Eastern Europe	No	Serbia	Southern Europe	No
Denmark	Northern Europe	Yes	Slovenia	Southern Europe	Yes
Estonia	Northern Europe	Yes	Spain	Southern Europe	Yes
Finland	Northern Europe	Yes	Austria	Western Europe	Yes
Iceland	Northern Europe	No	Belgium	Western Europe	Yes
Ireland	Northern Europe	Yes	France	Western Europe	Yes
Latvia	Northern Europe	Yes	Germany	Western Europe	Yes
Lithuania	Northern Europe	Yes	Luxembourg	Western Europe	Yes
Norway	Northern Europe	No	Netherlands	Western Europe	Yes
Sweden	Northern Europe	Yes	Switzerland	Western Europe	No
United Kingdom	Northern Europe	No			

2.5 Mobilising policy relevant species checklists results - subtask 2.2.2 (in WP2)

2.5.1 Interpretation Manual of European Union habitats Raw list (Annex 1)

The species list of the Interpretation Manual of European Union habitats Raw list was published on ChecklistBank (checklistbank.org/dataset/313964/about, Fig 2.) under a CC0 license to ensure free access, reuse, and distribution without restriction. This openness enables researchers, policymakers, and citizens across the EU and the world to consistently reference and integrate the Directive's provisions into their work. The published list comprises 4,366 names associated with 228 of the 233 habitat types defined under the EU Habitats Directive. Of these, 3,110 are unique scientific names. The remaining five habitat types have no characteristic species listed (e.g. Habitat 8340 Permanent glaciers). A detailed breakdown of the number of genera, species, and subspecies represented per habitat is provided in [Annex 2](#).

The figure consists of two side-by-side screenshots of the ChecklistBank interface. The left screenshot shows the metadata page for the dataset 'EU Habitats Directive, Raw Taxon List from the Interpretation Manual'. The metadata includes: Title: EU Habitats Directive, Raw Taxon List from the Interpretation Manual; DOI: 10.1001/2026-01-27; Description: This dataset captures the scientific names that characterize the habitat types listed in Annex I of the EU Habitats Directive, as described in the Interpretation Manual. Annex I defines 233 habitat types of Community interest, including 71 priority habitats, and constitutes the official, legally adopted reference for habitat conservation, assessment, and reporting across the European Union. The dataset preserves the scientific taxon names explicitly referenced in the Interpretation Manual and related official materials, maintaining a clear link between habitat definitions and their biological components. The extracted list is published and supported by the European Environment Agency (EEA), and is intended to promote transparency, reproducibility, and interoperability in biodiversity informatics, without constituting a taxonomically reviewed or updated species list, and therefore without implying taxonomic endorsement or suitability for immediate scientific or analytical use beyond the original legal and interpretative context. Version / Issued: 1.0 / 2026-01-27; Contact: No information; Publisher: The European Environment Agency (EEA); Creator: No information; Editor: No information. The right screenshot shows a classification tree view of the dataset. It lists taxonomic groups and their corresponding species counts: Kingdom: Animalia - 179 species; Kingdom: Fungi - 27 species; Kingdom: Plantae - 2,523 species. The Plantae group is further broken down into orders, families, and genera, with their respective species counts.

Figure 2. Metadata and classification tree view of the Interpretation Manual of the European Union habitats Raw list published published on ChecklistBank checklistbank.org/dataset/313964/about

The taxonomic composition is strongly dominated by Plantae, which accounts for 4,275 names (94.2%), followed by Animalia with 227 names (5.0%) and Fungi with 35 names (0.8%). There are several plant species names that are characteristics of multiple habitats, these are represented in Table 4.

Table 4: Top ten species scientific names represented more frequently across the species characterising Habitats Directive Annex I habitat types.

Scientific Name	# of habitats present
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	21
<i>Quercus robur</i>	18
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	18
<i>Picea abies</i>	16
<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>	15
<i>Festuca ovina</i>	13
<i>Quercus petraea</i>	13
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	13
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	13
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	12

2.5.1 Habitats Directive, Legal Annexes II, IV, V

The specific list of annexes II, IV, V of the Habitats Directive were published on ChecklistBank (Table 5) under a CC0 license to ensure free access, reuse, and distribution without restriction.

Table 5: Summary of the extraction of annexes II, IV, V of the habitats directive.

Annex	Scope	Link to published list	# of Names	# of species
<i>Annex II</i>	Animal and plant species of community interest whose conservation requires the designation of special areas of conservation	checklistbank.org/dataset/314298/	1,068	825
<i>Annex IV</i>	Animal and plant species of community interest in need of strict protection	checklistbank.org/dataset/314304/	1,127	884
<i>Annex V</i>	Animal and plant species of community interest whose taking in the wild and exploitation may be subject to management measures	checklistbank.org/dataset/314308/	149	61

These three datasets will serve as an interoperable reference for the legal information contained in the Habitats Directive. They preserve the scientific taxon names exactly as they appear in the Directive, including any typographical errors and outdated taxonomic information. As such, this list should be used

primarily as a legal reference aligned with the official document of the European Commission. For scientific purposes, a second version of the list will be developed, taking into account the countries' reports and taxonomic harmonization with ChecklistBank.

3. Further work

Building on the current results of the Habitats Directive, a new, independently constructed species list will be generated directly from the raw habitat source material. This process will involve systematic correction of orthographic errors, resolution of internal inconsistencies, and full harmonisation of scientific names with the Catalogue of Life to ensure alignment with current, accepted taxonomy. Harmonisation will include the assignment of accepted names and the application of the Catalogue of Life taxonomic classification to each scientific name. The resulting list will constitute a consistent and authoritative reference suitable for scientific analysis, policy reporting, and long-term reuse. This work will be detailed on the deliverables of Biodiversity Meets Data Work Package 3.

An equivalent methodology will subsequently be applied to the Birds Directive, and the Invasive Alien Species Regulation, following the same extraction, quality control, taxonomic classification, and harmonisation procedures to ensure coherence across EU nature conservation legislation.

4. Acknowledgements

We extend our special thanks to Mette Palitzsch Lund of the European Environment Agency (EEA) for kindly guiding us through the nuances of the Habitats Directive.

5. References

Bánki, O., Roskov, Y., Döring, M., Ower, G., Hernández Robles, D. R., Plata Corredor, C. A., Stjernaard Jeppesen, T., Örn, A., Pape, T., Hobern, D., Garnett, S., Little, H., DeWalt, R. E., Miller, J., Orrell, T., Aalbu, R., Abbott, J., Abreu, C., Acero P, A., et al. (2026). Catalogue of Life (2026-01-16 XR). Catalogue of Life Foundation, Amsterdam, Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.48580/dgw64>

Costello, M. J., DeWalt, R. E., Orrell, T., & Bánki, O. (2022). Two million species catalogued by 500 experts. *Nature*, 601(7892), 191. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-00010-z>

European Environment Agency (EEA). (n.d.). *About the European Environment Agency*. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/about-us>

European Environment Agency (EEA). (2020). *The European environment — state and outlook 2020 (SOER 2020)*. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/soer>

European Environment Agency (EEA). (n.d.). *EU nature legislation: Habitats Directive*. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/biodiversity/eu-nature-legislation/habitats-directive>

European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (1992). *Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (Habitats Directive)*. *Official Journal of the European Communities*, L 206, 7–50.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31992L0043>

European Environment Agency (EEA). (2020). *State of nature in the EU: Results from reporting under the nature directives 2013–2018*. EEA Report No 10/2020. European Environment Agency.

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/state-of-nature-in-the-eu-2020>

European Environment Agency (EEA). (n.d.). *Reporting under Article 17 of the Habitats Directive*. European Environment Agency.

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/biodiversity/eu-nature-legislation/article-17-reporting>

6. Annexes

Annex 1

Scientific Name extraction prompt used on ChatGPT-5.2 used to process the Habitats directive lists, as stored on the chat memory:

Extraction Protocol — Habitat Text → Taxon CSV (Reflecting User-Defined Rules Only)

Operational Definition

This task is a literal scientific-name extraction from Natura 2000 habitat descriptions, excluding vegetation syntaxa and structural text elements, preserving infraspecific rank notation, and formatting results into a controlled CSV schema.

1. Scope of Extraction

Extract only explicitly written scientific taxon names from habitat descriptions. Included:

- Any organism group if a scientific Latin name is explicitly written
- Plants
- Animals
- Bryophytes
- Lycopods
- Lichens
- Any other taxa if explicitly present in binomial or infraspecific format

There is no kingdom-based exclusion rule.

2. What Qualifies as a Valid Scientific Name

A name must:

1. Be explicitly written in the source text
2. Be in Latin scientific format
3. Not be inferred beyond unambiguous abbreviation expansion

Valid formats:

Format	Example	Extracted As
Genus	<i>Vaccinium spp.</i>	<i>Vaccinium</i>
Species	<i>Dryas octopetala</i>	<i>Dryas octopetala</i>
Subspecies	<i>Astragalus creticus ssp. creticus</i>	<i>Astragalus creticus subsp. creticus</i>
Variety	<i>Astragalus trojanus var. chius</i>	<i>Astragalus trojanus var. chius</i>

3. Explicit Exclusions

3.1 Syntaxonomic Units (ALWAYS EXCLUDED)

Do NOT extract vegetation syntaxa, including:

- Alliances
- Associations
- Subassociations

Examples:

- Loiseleurio-Vaccinion
- Rhododendro-Vaccinion
- Juniperion nanae
- Empetro-Vaccinietum
- Mugo-Rhodoretum hirsuti
- Larici-Cembretum

3.2 Structural / Editorial Elements (EXCLUDED)

- Habitat subtype codes (31.41, 31.7E, etc.)
- PAL.CLASS numbers
- Section headings
- Narrative descriptions
- Geographic phrases

4. Handling of Abbreviations

4.1 Abbreviated Genera

Abbreviations (e.g., *A. angustifolius*) may be expanded only if unambiguous within the same contextual block. If ambiguity exists → do not infer.

4.2 “spp.” Rule

If written as:

- *Vaccinium* spp.
- *Genista* spp.

Extract:

- scientificName = *Vaccinium*
- rank = genus

Do not infer species.

5. Intraspecific Names

5.1 Embedded in scientificName

Subspecies and varieties must be written inside the scientificName field:

- *Astragalus creticus* subsp. *creticus*
- *Astragalus trojanus* var. *chius*

5.2 Rank Column Values

Case	Rank
Genus only	genus
Species	species
Subspecies	subspecies
Variety	variety

5.3 Normalization

- *ssp.* → normalized to *subsp.*
- *var.* retained
- No additional nomenclatural corrections

6. No Taxonomic Interpretation

Extraction is strictly literal. Do NOT:

- Correct spelling
- Update taxonomy
- Merge synonyms
- Validate against databases
- Infer missing epithets
- Invent taxa

7. No Deduplication Unless Requested

- Names are kept as written.
- Species and infraspecific taxa are not collapsed.

- Cross-habitat deduplication only performed if explicitly requested.

8. Output Format

Strict CSV schema:

habitat_ID,habitatName,scientificName,kingdom,rank,comments

Field Definitions

- habitat_ID → numeric habitat code
- habitatName → exact habitat title
- scientificName → full taxon name (including infraspecific rank when applicable)
- kingdom → filled only when clearly known; otherwise may remain blank
- rank → genus / species / subspecies / variety
- comments → empty unless explicitly instructed otherwise

9. Inclusion Logic Summary

Case	Action
Latin binomial present	Extract
Genus spp.	Extract genus
Subspecies written	Extract full trinomial
Variety written	Extract full name
Syntaxon	Exclude
Habitat code	Exclude
Narrative text	Exclude
Geographic reference	Exclude

Annex 2

549 published checklists Invasive species list on ChecklistBank identified.

ID	Title	Region	license
290643	DNA barcoding revealed the presence of the invasive freshwater mussel <i>Sinanodonta</i> aff. <i>woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834) in Afghanistan	Southern Asia	cc0
300348	Five alien achatinid land snails (Gastropoda, Eupulmonata) first reported in greenhouses of Italian botanical gardens	-	cc0
289980	List of invasive flora and fauna species from the territory of Ukraine	Eastern Europe	cc0
20830	Catálogo Español de Especies Exóticas Invasoras. Relación de táxones correspondientes a las Islas Baleares	Southern Europe	cc by
20831	Catálogo Español de Especies Exóticas Invasoras. Relación de táxones correspondientes a las Islas Canarias	Southern Europe	cc by
2436	Catálogo Español de Especies Exóticas Invasoras. Relación de táxones correspondientes al territorio peninsular del Estado español	Southern Europe	cc by
312243	List of Alien Species in South Africa 2025	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
26227	Invasive Alien Plant Species in Tanzania	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by nc
21628	Invasive Alien Species in Sweden (Regulation (EU) 1143/2014)	Northern Europe	cc0
21627	Risk assessment of invasive taxa in Sweden	Northern Europe	cc0
280642	List of invasive exotic species not yet widely distributed in Wallonia	Western Europe	cc by nc
289588	Checklist of alien mammals of Belgium	Western Europe	cc0
7648	Checklist of alien herpetofauna of Belgium	Western Europe	cc0
58406	List of Invasive Alien Species of Union concern	Western Europe	cc0
29350	Ad hoc checklist of alien species in Belgium	Western Europe	cc0
310808	<i>Corythucha arcuata</i> (Say, 1832) (Hemiptera, Tingidae) an invasive pest, with a review of the recent invasion of alien species to Kosovo	-	cc0
281329	New records of two cusk eels of the genus <i>Neobythites</i> from Taiwan, with a northward range extension of <i>N. australiensis</i> Nielsen, 2002 (Actinopterygii: Ophidiiformes: Ophidiidae)	-	cc0
270510	A comprehensive update on the morphology and distribution of the invasive scaffold-web spider <i>Eidmannella pallida</i> (Araneae, Nesticidae) with a focus on new records from Italy	Southern Europe	cc0
277680	Taxonomic revision of the <i>Erigeron acris</i> group (Asteraceae) in Murmansk Region, Russia, reveals a complex pattern of native and alien taxa	-	cc0
288267	The alien synanthropic Salticidae in Brazil (Araneae)	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0

163376	Joppeicus paradoxus (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Joppeicidae): a new alien species in the European Union?	-	cc0
306668	Blumea axillaris (Inuleae, Asteraceae): the first record of an invasive exotic weed in the Americas and the first record of the genus in Brazil	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
270510	A comprehensive update on the morphology and distribution of the invasive scaffold-web spider Eidmannella pallida (Araneae, Nesticidae) with a focus on new records from Italy	Southern Europe	cc0
307587	Formorsaneleotris hualienensis, a new genus and species of inland water sleeper (Teleostei: Eleotridae) from eastern Taiwan	-	cc0
158619	First record of three alien Auchenorrhyncha species from Europe: Acanalonia bivittata (Say, 1825), Branchana xanthota Li, 2011, and Dryadomorpha pallida Kirkaldy 1906 (Hemiptera: Auchenorrhyncha: Acanaloniidae, Cicadellidae)	-	cc0
286003	A new widely distributed invasive alien species of Amasa ambrosia beetles (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae: Xyleborini)	-	cc0
278920	How complex is the Naineris setosa species complex? First integrative study of a presumed cosmopolitan and invasive annelid (Sedentaria: Orbiniidae)	-	cc0
295361	Reevaluation of taxonomic identity of the recently introduced invasive planthopper, Pochazia shantungensis (Chou & Lu, 1977) (Hemiptera: Fulgoroidea: Ricaniidae) in Japan	Eastern Asia	cc0
311434	Stropharia daliensis sp. nov. (Strophariaceae, Agaricales) from Yunnan Province, China	Eastern Asia	cc0
309640	Notas Herpetologicas, Iv El Genero Melanophryniscus (Amphibia, Salientia En El Uruguay, Con Descripcion De Dos Nuevas Especies	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
282349	Review of the chewing louse fauna of the invasive common myna (Acridotheres tristis), with new records from Palestine and a redescription of Brueelia chayanh Ansari, 1955 (Phthiraptera, Ischnocera, Brueelia-complex)	-	cc0
298195	The extension of the distributional range of an invasive mussel, Mytilus galloprovincialis (Bivalvia: Mytilidae) in the Sea of Japan	Eastern Asia	cc0
310614	The distribution, origins and taxonomy of Tricellaria inopinata d'Hondt and Occhipinti Ambrogi, 1985, an invasive bryozoan new to the Atlantic	-	cc0
163376	Joppeicus paradoxus (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Joppeicidae): a new alien species in the European Union?	-	cc0
270510	A comprehensive update on the morphology and distribution of the invasive scaffold-web spider Eidmannella pallida (Araneae, Nesticidae) with a focus on new records from Italy	Southern Europe	cc0
295159	Intriguing additions of exotic and invasive ants to The Gambia (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc0
311434	Stropharia daliensis sp. nov. (Strophariaceae, Agaricales) from Yunnan Province, China	Eastern Asia	cc0
309640	Notas Herpetologicas, Iv El Genero Melanophryniscus (Amphibia, Salientia En El Uruguay, Con Descripcion De Dos Nuevas Especies	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
282349	Review of the chewing louse fauna of the invasive common myna (Acridotheres tristis), with new records from Palestine and a redescription of Brueelia chayanh Ansari, 1955 (Phthiraptera, Ischnocera, Brueelia-complex)	-	cc0
297306	A morphological and molecular study of Ligia exotica Roux, 1828 (Crustacea: Isopoda: Ligiidae) from Japan, with descriptions of two new species	Eastern Asia	cc0

313203	New locality of the invasive Monk parakeet <i>Myiopsitta monachus</i> (Boddaert, 1783) in Greece	Southern Europe	cc0
310804	First report of an exotic sap beetle, <i>Phenolia (Lasiodites) picta</i> (Macleay, 1825) (Coleoptera, Nitidulidae) from Iran with notes on its distribution range and damage on different hosts	-	cc0
4197	New Japanese Record of the Rare Cusk Eel <i>Benthocometes australiensis</i> (Actinopterygii: Ophidiiformes: Ophidiidae), a First Record of the Species from the Northern Hemisphere	-	cc0
308516	A new invasive freshwater mussel: Discovery of a non-native population of <i>Pilsbryconcha exilis</i> (Lea, 1838) in Myanmar (Bivalvia: Unionidae)	South-eastern Asia	cc0
314030	A new family of freshwater ascomycetes from Australia: Rivulataceae fam. nov., <i>Rivulatus australiensis</i> gen. et. sp. nov. (Diaporthomycetidae)	Australia and New Zealand	cc0
294445	Records about the alien millipede <i>Oxidus gracilis</i> (C. L. Koch, 1847) (Diplopoda: Polydesmida: Paradoxosomatidae) in continental Chile	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
303137	First record of the invasive bumble bee <i>Bombus terrestris</i> (Hymenoptera: Apidae) on Navarino Island, southern Chile (55 ° S)	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
313861	A new species of the New Zealand endemic weevil genus <i>Clypeolus</i> Broun (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Cryptorhynchinae), found attacking an invasive weed, white horehound (<i>Marrubium vulgare</i> L. Lamiales: Lamiaceae)	Australia and New Zealand	cc0
292746	Die bisher in Italien gefundenen freilebenden Erd und Süßwasser-Nematoden.	-	cc0
299071	New Alien Mediterranean Biodiversity Records (March 2021)	-	cc0
313861	A new species of the New Zealand endemic weevil genus <i>Clypeolus</i> Broun (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Cryptorhynchinae), found attacking an invasive weed, white horehound (<i>Marrubium vulgare</i> L. Lamiales: Lamiaceae)	Australia and New Zealand	cc0
292746	Die bisher in Italien gefundenen freilebenden Erd und Süßwasser-Nematoden.	-	cc0
299071	New Alien Mediterranean Biodiversity Records (March 2021)	-	cc0
310804	First report of an exotic sap beetle, <i>Phenolia (Lasiodites) picta</i> (Macleay, 1825) (Coleoptera, Nitidulidae) from Iran with notes on its distribution range and damage on different hosts	-	cc0
4197	New Japanese Record of the Rare Cusk Eel <i>Benthocometes australiensis</i> (Actinopterygii: Ophidiiformes: Ophidiidae), a First Record of the Species from the Northern Hemisphere	-	cc0
310283	A new and earlier record of <i>Chrysomya megacephala</i> in South Africa, with notes on another exotic species, <i>Calliphora vicina</i> (Diptera: Calliphoridae)	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc0
306668	<i>Blumea axillaris</i> (Inuleae, Asteraceae): the first record of an invasive exotic weed in the Americas and the first record of the genus in Brazil	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
299556	History of knotweed (<i>Follopia</i> spp.) invasiveness	-	cc0
313861	A new species of the New Zealand endemic weevil genus <i>Clypeolus</i> Broun (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Cryptorhynchinae), found attacking an invasive weed, white horehound (<i>Marrubium vulgare</i> L. Lamiales: Lamiaceae)	Australia and New Zealand	cc0
299071	New Alien Mediterranean Biodiversity Records (March 2021)	-	cc0
311434	<i>Stropharia daliensis</i> sp. nov. (Strophariaceae, Agaricales) from Yunnan Province, China	Eastern Asia	cc0

309640	Notas Herpetologicas, Iv El Genero Melanophryniscus (Amphibia, Salientia En El Uruguay, Con Descripcion De Dos Nuevas Especies	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
282349	Review of the chewing louse fauna of the invasive common myna (<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>), with new records from Palestine and a redescription of <i>Brueelia chayanh</i> Ansari, 1955 (Phthiraptera, Ischnocera, <i>Brueelia</i> -complex)	-	cc0
2594	<i>Oreonebria</i> (<i>Oreonebria</i>) <i>soror tresignore</i> ssp. nov. vom Pizzo dei Tre Signori in der Lombardei, Italien (Coleoptera: Carabidae, <i>Nebriinae</i>)	-	cc0
51796	Insectorum novorum exoticorum (ex ordine Dipteorum) descriptiones	-	cc0
5013	A new parasitoid (Hymenoptera: Braconidae: Aphidiinae) of the invasive bamboo aphids <i>Takecallis</i> spp. (Hemiptera: Aphididae) from Western Europe	-	cc0
51796	Insectorum novorum exoticorum (ex ordine Dipteorum) descriptiones	-	cc0
2594	<i>Oreonebria</i> (<i>Oreonebria</i>) <i>soror tresignore</i> ssp. nov. vom Pizzo dei Tre Signori in der Lombardei, Italien (Coleoptera: Carabidae, <i>Nebriinae</i>)	-	cc0
264160	Cicadidae (Homoptera) de Nicaragua: Catalogo ilustrado, incluyendo especies exóticas del Museo Entomológico de Leon	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
7109	Alien Gill Parasites of the Silver Carp <i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i> (Cypriniformes: Cyprinidae) in Tochigi Prefecture, Central Japan	Eastern Asia	cc0
24021	Rediscovery of the Hawaiian endemic bark beetle <i>Xyleborus pleiades</i> Samulesoni 1981 on Moloka'i with records of three new exotic bark beetles for the island (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae: <i>Xyleborini</i>)	-	cc0
2594	<i>Oreonebria</i> (<i>Oreonebria</i>) <i>soror tresignore</i> ssp. nov. vom Pizzo dei Tre Signori in der Lombardei, Italien (Coleoptera: Carabidae, <i>Nebriinae</i>)	-	cc0
51796	Insectorum novorum exoticorum (ex ordine Dipteorum) descriptiones	-	cc0
138780	The taxonomy and nomenclature of <i>Kalanchoe</i> × <i>vadensis</i> [<i>K. blossfeldiana</i> × <i>K. marmorata</i> var. <i>somaliensis</i>] (Crassulaceae subfam. <i>Kalanchooideae</i>), an early nothospecies produced in The Netherlands in the 1950 s	-	cc0
4606	New records of <i>Scotomedes alienus sikkimensis</i> (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Velocipedidae) from Nepal	Southern Asia	cc0
51610	An emendation of the generic diagnosis of the monotypic <i>Glanitaenia</i> (Cestoda: Proteocephalidae), with notes on the geographical distribution of <i>G. osculata</i> , a parasite of invasive wels catfish	-	cc0
221145	Beitrag zur Zoogeographie einiger Oxypoda-Arten aus Italien mit Beschreibung einer neuen Art der Untergattung <i>Thliboptera</i> STEPHENS, 1839 (Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Aleocharinae)	-	cc0
37890	Zweyter Theil, enthält Beschreibungen verschiedener wichtiger Naturalien	-	cc0
8100	Ultra-Conserved Element Phylogenomics of New World <i>Ponera</i> (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) Illuminates the Origin and Phylogeographic History of the Endemic Exotic Ant <i>Ponera exotica</i>	-	cc0
53273	<i>Stictoleptura cordigera</i> (Füssli, 1775) (Cerambycidae: Lepturinae: Lepturini), a new alien longhorn beetle introduced in Chile	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
33439	Exotic ants (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) of Ohio	-	cc0
21587	<i>Trioxys liui</i> Chou & Chou, 1993 (Hymenoptera, Braconidae, Aphidiinae): an invasive aphid parasitoid attacking invasive <i>Takecallis</i> species (Hemiptera, Aphididae) in the Iberian Peninsula	-	cc0

30179	A taxonomic revision helps to clarify differences between the Atlantic invasive <i>Ptilohyalelittoralis</i> and the Mediterranean endemic <i>Parhyaleplumicornis</i> (Crustacea, Amphipoda)	-	cc0
57647	Taxonomic identity of <i>Distaplia stylifera</i> (Tunicata, Ascidiacea), a new arrival to the eastern Pacific displaying invasive behavior in the Gulf of California, Mexico	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
20953	Exotic-looking Neotropical Tischeriidae (Lepidoptera) and their host plants	-	cc0
33102	Rediscovery of <i>Histiopus alienus</i> Thomas, 1916 a century after its description (Chiroptera, Vespertilionidae): distribution extension and redescription	-	cc0
30979	New records of an alien aphid species <i>Tinocallis</i> (<i>Sappocallis</i>) <i>takachihoensis</i> from countries in central and northern Europe (Hemiptera, Aphididae, Calaphidinae)	-	cc0
6724	Revision of the <i>Plagiolepis schmitzii</i> group with description of <i>Pl. invadens</i> sp. nov. - a new invasive supercolonial species (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)	-	cc0
28182	First record of <i>Aequoreamacrodactyla</i> (Cnidaria, Hydrozoa) from the Israeli coast of the eastern Mediterranean Sea, an alien species indicating invasive pathways	-	cc0
9749	A new species of <i>Cheiloneurus</i> Westwood (Hymenoptera, Encyrtidae) as a hyperparasitoid of the invasive cotton mealybug, <i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> Tinsley, in China	Eastern Asia	cc0
2506	Redelimitation of <i>Heteroradulum</i> (Auriculariales, Basidiomycota) with <i>H. australiense</i> sp. nov.	-	cc0
33439	Exotic ants (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) of Ohio	-	cc0
26238	Updated taxonomy of <i>Lactifluus</i> section <i>Luteoli</i> : <i>L. russulisporus</i> from Australia and <i>L. caliendri</i> from Thailand		cc0
25378	Six years of fruit fly surveys in Bangladesh: a new species, 33 new country records and discovery of the highly invasive <i>Bactrocera carambolae</i> (Diptera, Tephritidae)	Southern Asia	cc0
33102	Rediscovery of <i>Histiopus alienus</i> Thomas, 1916 a century after its description (Chiroptera, Vespertilionidae): distribution extension and redescription	-	cc0
30979	New records of an alien aphid species <i>Tinocallis</i> (<i>Sappocallis</i>) <i>takachihoensis</i> from countries in central and northern Europe (Hemiptera, Aphididae, Calaphidinae)	-	cc0
6724	Revision of the <i>Plagiolepis schmitzii</i> group with description of <i>Pl. invadens</i> sp. nov. - a new invasive supercolonial species (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)	-	cc0
7819	Identity of parasitoid wasps (Hymenoptera, Braconidae and Eulophidae) reared from aquatic leaf-mining flies (Diptera, Ephydriidae) on invasive Brazilian waterweed <i>Egeria densa</i> in South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc0
35282	First record in the Tropical Eastern Pacific of the exotic species <i>Ficopomatus uschakovi</i> (Polychaeta, Serpulidae)	-	cc0
279998	First record of <i>Aequoreamacrodactyla</i> (Cnidaria, Hydrozoa) from the Israeli coast of the eastern Mediterranean Sea, an alien species indicating invasive pathways	-	cc0
26827	Revision der <i>Nematopogonadansonella</i> -Artengruppe mit Beschreibung einer neuen Art aus den Bergregionen Sueditaliens (Lepidoptera, Adelidae)	-	cc0
35728	Taxonomic synopsis of invasive and native <i>Spartina</i> (Poaceae, Chloridoideae) in the Pacific Northwest (British Columbia, Washington and Oregon), including the first report of <i>Spartina xtownsendii</i> for British Columbia, Canada	Northern America	cc0
20574	Spermatophyta and invasive plants in Wanda Mountains, Heilongjiang Province, China	Eastern Asia	cc by nc
189821	Spermatophyta_and_invasive_alien_plants_of_Wanda_Mountains_in_China_a_first_checklist	Eastern Asia	cc by nc
312120	Lista de especies exóticas declaradas como invasoras en Colombia - Resolución 0067 de 2023 expedida por el Ministerio de Ambiente y Desarrollo Sostenible	Latin America	cc0

		and the Caribbean	
311287	Especies introducidas, exóticas, trasplantadas, invasoras y potencialmente invasoras obtenidas a partir de fuentes primarias y secundarias, incorporadas en el diagnóstico del Plan Nacional de Prevención, Control y Manejo	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by nc
62930	The checklist of alien seed plants of D.R. Congo, based on evidence from herbarium collections	Western Europe	cc0
23829	Two new Amphilochida (Amphipoda: Amphilochidea) associated with the bioinvasive Tubastraea coccinea from Todos-os-Santos Bay, Bahia State, Brazil	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
47983	New scale insect (Hemiptera: Sternorrhyncha: Coccoidea) records from Fiji: three new species, records of several new invasive species and an updated checklist of Coccoidea	Melanesia	cc0
32346	Another alien on the horizon? First European record of Tautoneura polymitusa, an East Asian leafhopper (Hemiptera: Auchenorrhyncha: Cicadellidae)	-	cc0
44103	Cladocerans of genus Alona Baird, 1843 (Cladocera: Anomopoda: Chydoridae) and related genera from Aguascalientes State, Mexico	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
106157	Morphological diversification of alien and native aquatic snails of the genus Physa and Aplexa (Gastropoda: Physidae) of Western and Central European range	-	cc0
23604	Coccygidium transcasicum (Kokujev) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) parasitizing larvae of invasive pest Spodoptera frugiperda (J. E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in India	Southern Asia	cc0
239615	Epibiotic association of encrusting cheilostome bryozoans on shells of an invasive mussel from rocky shores of South Africa, with the description of a new aviculiferous species of Chaperia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc0
45932	A probably invasive new genus and new species of soft coral (Octocorallia: Alcyonacea: Clavulariidae) from Brazil	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
40345	Taxonomic revision of the Pegomya meridiana species group (Diptera: Anthomyiidae) including natural enemies of invasive Hypericum spp. (Clusiaceae)	-	cc0
41024	Recent discoveries of alien Watersipora (Bryozoa) in Western Europe, with redescrptions of species	Western Europe	cc0
5560	Another new exotic bark beetle in Florida: Ernoporus parvulus (Eggers, 1943) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae), with additional taxonomic changes	-	cc0
40345	Taxonomic revision of the Pegomya meridiana species group (Diptera: Anthomyiidae) including natural enemies of invasive Hypericum spp. (Clusiaceae)	-	cc0
40031	A new species of the genus Alienates Barber (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Enicocephalidae: Alienatinae) from Venezuela	-	cc0
27398	A redescription of Moina australiensis Sars, 1896 (Cladocera: Moinidae) with short notes on Australian moinids	-	cc0
5560	Another new exotic bark beetle in Florida: Ernoporus parvulus (Eggers, 1943) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae), with additional taxonomic changes	-	cc0
47054	On the evolution of the species complex Pachycondyla chinensis (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Ponerinae), including the origin of its invasive form and description of a new species	-	cc0
41156	Biflustra perambulata n. sp. (Cheilostomata: Bryozoa), a new alien species from Cochin Harbour, Kerala, India	Southern Asia	cc0

41024	Recent discoveries of alien Watersipora (Bryozoa) in Western Europe, with redescrptions of species	-	cc0
40902	A new species of invasive gall wasp (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae: Tetrastichinae) on blue gum (Eucalyptus globulus) in California	-	cc0
38700	The Westpalaeartic Lasius paralienus complex (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) contains three species	-	cc0
53676	An annotated checklist of terrestrial flatworms (Platyhelminthes: Tricladida: Geoplanidae) from Mexico, with new records of invasive species from a citizen science platform and a new nomen dubium	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
20272	The worrying arrival of the invasive Asian needle ant Brachyponera chinensis in Europe (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)	Europe	cc0
38755	Narcine baliensis, a new species of electric ray from southeast Asia (Chondrichthyes: Torpediniformes)	-	cc0
40031	A new species of the genus Alienates Barber (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Enicocephalidae: Alienatinae) from Venezuela	-	cc0
8813	Erythropodium caribaeorum (Duchassaing and Michelotti, 1860) (Cnidaria Alcyonacea), an additional alien coral in the Southwestern Atlantic	-	cc0
41476	Phloeocharis subtilissima Mannerheim (Staphylinidae: Phloeocharinae) and Cephennium gallicum Ganglbauer (Scydmaenidae) new to North America: a case study in the introduction of exotic Coleoptera to the port of Halifax, with new records of other species	-	cc0
43021	Description of a new species of Anagyrus Howard (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Encyrtidae), a promising biological control agent of the invasive Madeira mealybug, Phenacoccus madeirensis Green (Hemiptera: Sternorrhyncha: Pseudococcidae)	-	cc0
43021	Description of a new species of Anagyrus Howard (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Encyrtidae), a promising biological control agent of the invasive Madeira mealybug, Phenacoccus madeirensis Green (Hemiptera: Sternorrhyncha: Pseudococcidae)	-	cc0
40031	A new species of the genus Alienates Barber (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Enicocephalidae: Alienatinae) from Venezuela	-	cc0
40902	A new species of invasive gall wasp (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae: Tetrastichinae) on blue gum (Eucalyptus globulus) in California	-	cc0
38700	The Westpalaeartic Lasius paralienus complex (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) contains three species	-	cc0
5355	Two new Aprostocetus species (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae: Tetrastichinae), fortuitous parasitoids of invasive eulophid gall inducers (Tetrastichinae) on Eucalyptus and Erythrina	-	cc0
33007	A description of three new species of the genus Alienia Fibiger, 2011 from Southeast Asia (Lepidoptera, Erebidae, Hyphenodinae: Micronoctuini)	-	cc0
8258	Ptilodactyla exotica Chapin, 1927 in Italy (Coleoptera: Ptilodactylidae)	Southern Europe	cc0
30773	A new blind snake of the genus Lethoebia (Serpentes: Typhlopidae) from Rwanda with redescrptions of L. gracilis (Sternfeld, 1910) and L. graueri (Sternfeld, 1912) and the introduction of a non-invasive preparation procedure for scanning electron microscopy in zoology	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc0
54024	Monogenea on exotic Indian freshwater fish. 5. First report of pathogenic Gussevia asota (Platyhelminths) from Oscar Astronotus ocellatus (Agassiz 1831) (Perciformes: Cichlidae)	-	cc0
7685	A new species and genus of Alienopteridae (Blattodea) from mid-Cretaceous amber of northern Myanmar	South-eastern Asia	cc0
26821	Another alien terrestrial planarian in the United Kingdom: Australopacifica atrata (Steel, 1897) (Platyhelminthes: Tricladida: Continenticola)	-	cc0

27335	Description of the larvae of <i>Cotinis aliena</i> Woodruff, 2008 (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Cetoniinae: Gymnetini), with a key to the known larvae of New World Gymnetini	-	cc0
40218	A new invasive weed-feeding species of <i>Polypedilum</i> (<i>Pentapedilum</i>) Kieffer from South Africa (Diptera: Chironomidae, Chironominae)	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc0
26339	<i>Deroplax silphoides</i> (Thunberg, 1783) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Scutelleridae) Invasive Species in Egypt with additional morphological and behavioral data	Northern Africa	cc0
45932	A probably invasive new genus and new species of soft coral (Octocorallia: Alcyonacea: Clavulariidae) from Brazil	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
38700	The Westpalaearctic <i>Lasius paralienus</i> complex (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) contains three species	-	cc0
24177	The identity of the invasive yellow-striped terrestrial planarian found recently in Europe: <i>Caenoplana variegata</i> (Fletcher & Hamilton, 1888) or <i>Caenoplana bicolor</i> (Graff, 1899)?	Europe	cc0
23481	First record of the alien bamboo leafhopper, <i>Branchana xanthota</i> , in Japan (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae: Deltocephalinae)	Eastern Asia	cc0
37015	First European records of an alien paper wasp: <i>Polistes</i> (<i>Aphanilopterus</i>) <i>major</i> Palisot de Beauvois, 1818 (Hymenoptera: Vespidae) in northern Spain	Southern Europe	cc0
23561	<i>Archophileurus spinosus</i> Dechambre, 2006 (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Dynastinae), a new exotic scarab possibly acclimatized in Italy, with a compilation of exotic Scarabaeidae found in Europe	Southern Europe	cc0
24177	The identity of the invasive yellow-striped terrestrial planarian found recently in Europe: <i>Caenoplana variegata</i> (Fletcher & Hamilton, 1888) or <i>Caenoplana bicolor</i> (Graff, 1899)?	-	cc0
44987	A new invasive <i>Ptinella</i> Motschulsky from Europe and North America (Coleoptera: Ptiliidae)	-	cc0
44103	Cladocerans of genus <i>Alona</i> Baird, 1843 (Cladocera: Anomopoda: Chydoridae) and related genera from Aguascalientes State, Mexico	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
106157	Morphological diversification of alien and native aquatic snails of the genus <i>Physa</i> and <i>Aplexa</i> (Gastropoda: Physidae) of Western and Central European range	-	cc0
45932	A probably invasive new genus and new species of soft coral (Octocorallia: Alcyonacea: Clavulariidae) from Brazil	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc0
228177	A new Australian species of invasive psyllid, <i>Acizzia convector</i> Burckhardt & Taylor, sp. nov. (Psylloidea: Psyllidae) associated with <i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> and <i>A. mangium</i> (Fabaceae)	-	cc0
50602	<i>Laimaphelenchus australis</i> sp. nov. (Nematoda: Aphelenchina) from exotic pines, <i>Pinus radiata</i> and <i>P. pinaster</i> , in Australia	Australia and New Zealand	cc0
29601	Checklist derived from occurrence data published on invasive alien plant species on GBIF site	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
29602	Checklist derived from occurrence data published on threatened and invasive alien plant species on GBIF site	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
310361	Database of exotic insects in continental Chile	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by nc
283351	Alien plants of Kyrgyzstan	Central Asia	cc by

311584	Liturgusa maya (Mantodea, Liturgusidae), the first record of an alien praying mantis in the Galápagos Islands	-	cc0
293321	Rasgos físicos de semillas de cuatro especies potencialmente invasoras de un Bosque Altoandino disturbado	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by nc
3424	Listado de plantas vasculares nativas y exóticas presentes en Bogotá-Colombia con reportes de invasión en otras regiones tropicales	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by nc
58737	Checklist of Invasive Plants in Cuba - 2022	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
77918	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Netherlands	-	cc by
31966	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mongolia	Eastern Asia	cc by
24507	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Serbia	Southern Europe	cc by
77934	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Slovakia	Eastern Europe	cc by
23193	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bazaruto National Park, Mozambique	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23197	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Queen Elizabeth National Park, Uganda	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23373	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Aride Special Reserve, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23289	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kruger National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24484	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Guinea	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28948	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Portugal	Southern Europe	cc by
24499	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Papua New Guinea		cc by
28932	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bhutan	Southern Asia	cc by
55652	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Maloelap Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
30085	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kosrae, Federated States of Micronesia	-	cc by
28945	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Colombia	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23348	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Silhouette National Park, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23296	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Augrabies Falls National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by

24491	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Sierra Leone	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23286	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – British Indian Ocean Territory	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55643	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ujae Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
24532	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Japan	Eastern Asia	cc by
23240	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Malalotja Nature Reserve, Eswatini	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55648	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Namdrik Atoll Ramsar site, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
77945	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Paraguay	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23225	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Nyanga National Park, Zimbabwe	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77936	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Canada	Northern America	cc by
77941	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Lithuania	Northern Europe	cc by
105527	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tonga	Polynesia	cc by
24498	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - China	Eastern Asia	cc by
28806	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ukraine	Eastern Europe	cc by
23277	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mokala National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55696	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Aur Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
24516	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Syrian Arab Republic	Western Asia	cc by
28946	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Madeira, Portugal	Southern Europe	cc by
30412	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Afghanistan	Southern Asia	cc by
23290	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Karoo National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23242	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Archipelago Juan Fernández, Chile	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
30469	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Brazil	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
55646	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Rongdrik Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
77917	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Congo	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by

23361	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Islets of Farquhar Atoll, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24486	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Zambia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77957	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Laos	-	cc by
23283	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ascension Island, Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
31962	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Vanuatu	Melanesia	cc by
28947	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Azores, Portugal	Southern Europe	cc by
23375	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - African Banks, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24522	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Romania	Eastern Europe	cc by
28930	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Uzbekistan	Central Asia	cc by
28912	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Fuerteventura, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
28933	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Chad	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24475	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Iran	-	cc by
24488	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Gambia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28811	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Federated States of Micronesia	-	cc by
28956	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Galápagos Islands, Ecuador	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
28950	Global Register of Invasive and Introduced Species - Norway	Northern Europe	cc by
23370	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cousin Special Reserve, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77940	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tajikistan	Central Asia	cc by
23332	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mauritania	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
31945	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Yemen	Western Asia	cc by
55651	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mejit Island, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
27905	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Wallis and Futuna	Polynesia	cc by
24468	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
23294	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Camdeboo National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23275	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Namaqua National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by

24494	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Gabon	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23295	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bontebok National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24478	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Albania	Southern Europe	cc by
108058	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Atoll Nukulaelae, Tuvalu	Polynesia	cc by
28939	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Grand Cayman, Cayman Islands	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
77922	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Dominican Republic	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23226	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Serengeti - Mara Ecosystem (Kenya, Tanzania)	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55698	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ailuk Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
28804	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - French Southern and Antarctic Territories (TAAF), Scattered Islands - Îles Éparses, France	Western Europe	cc by
55640	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Wothe Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
28915	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - La Gomera, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
55655	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kwajalein Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23192	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Lutembe Bay Wetland System, Uganda	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28937	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cambodia	South-eastern Asia	cc by
24521	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Poland	Eastern Europe	cc by
23280	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bulgaria	Eastern Europe	cc by
28805	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Singapore	South-eastern Asia	cc by
23357	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mare-Aux-Cochons, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23365	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cousine Island, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23276	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mountain Zebra National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23303	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Montserrat	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
31956	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Chile	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by

28999	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Faroe Islands	Northern Europe	cc by
55639	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Wotje Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
28909	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Eswatini (Swaziland)	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23306	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Turkmenistan	Central Asia	cc by
23284	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Saint Helena, Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24482	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Niger	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28919	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Belarus	Eastern Europe	cc by
28944	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - State of Palestine	-	cc by
24492	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Senegal	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55656	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kili Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
77943	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bolivia	-	cc by
24496	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Sao Tome and Principe	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23228	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Serengeti National Park, Tanzania	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77947	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Peru	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
31964	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Myanmar	South-eastern Asia	cc by
23234	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ngorongoro Conservation Area, Tanzania	-	cc by
23363	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - D'Arros island, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77946	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Trinidad and Tobago	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
77924	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Azerbaijan	Western Asia	cc by
23326	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - French Guiana	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
28934	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Denmark	Northern Europe	cc by
27904	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Suriname	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by

23238	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Hawane Nature Reserve and Dam, Eswatini	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24514	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Malaysia	South-eastern Asia	cc by
23244	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Jeju Island, Republic of Korea	-	cc by
28942	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Iraq	Western Asia	cc by
77951	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Venezuela	-	cc by
28815	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ndzuwani (Anjouan), Comoros	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23287	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Turks and Caicos Islands	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
29000	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Chuuk, Federated States of Micronesia	-	cc by
25058	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Zimbabwe	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
31954	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Juan Fernandez Islands, Chile	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
24534	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Malta	Southern Europe	cc by
25060	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bosnia and Herzegovina	Southern Europe	cc by
23241	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Dongonab Bay - Marsa Waiai, Sudan	Northern Africa	cc by
24485	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kenya	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28954	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Pakistan	Southern Asia	cc by
77949	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Somalia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
31959	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23358	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - La Digue island, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28904	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Burkina Faso	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23246	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Socotra Archipelago, Yemen	Western Asia	cc by
23292	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Golden Gate Highlands National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23237	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mlawula Nature Reserve, Eswatini	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by

24506	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Switzerland	Western Europe	cc by
24517	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Eritrea	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28817	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Comoros	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24501	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Benin	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23198	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Victoria Falls National Park, Zimbabwe	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55653	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Majuro Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
55658	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Jaluit Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
25063	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Saint Kitts and Nevis	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23291	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kalahari Gemsbok National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77939	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Uruguay	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23298	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Addo-Elephant National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28935	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Botswana	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24483	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Côte d'Ivoire	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23245	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Lord Howe Island, Australia	Australia and New Zealand	cc by
28906	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - New Caledonia, France		cc by
29808	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bangladesh	Southern Asia	cc by
31952	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ireland	Northern Europe	cc by
28940	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cayman Brac, Cayman Islands	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23189	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Chimanimani National Park, Zimbabwe	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
31957	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Rapa Nui (Isla de Pascua, Easter Island)	-	cc by
77916	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Korea (Democratic People's Republic of)	-	cc by
23282	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tristan da Cunha, Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by

77925	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Clipperton Island, France	Western Europe	cc by
29119	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Saint Barthelemy	-	cc by
24513	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Panama	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
28936	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Democratic Republic of Congo	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28808	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Vietnam	-	cc by
55649	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Namdrik Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
107850	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tuvalu	Polynesia	cc by
26225	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mayotte, France		cc by
23243	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Galápagos Islands, Ecuador	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
24512	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Australia	Australia and New Zealand	cc by
23441	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Moldova	-	cc by
31960	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77956	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Grenada	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23297	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Agulhas National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77926	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Saint Pierre and Miquelon	Northern America	cc by
23355	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Port Launay Wetland, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24500	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Madagascar	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23350	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Praslin National Park, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
30169	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Niue	Polynesia	cc by
77954	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- San Marino	Southern Europe	cc by
28914	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Lanzarote, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
24471	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Armenia	Western Asia	cc by
23371	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Conception, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by

23268	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Prince Edward Island and Marion Island, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28908	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - North Macedonia	Southern Europe	cc by
29006	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Algeria	Northern Africa	cc by
28809	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Jordan	Western Asia	cc by
262223	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Likiep Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
307743	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Alaska, United States (ver.2.0, 2022)	-	cc0
108057	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Island Niulakita, Niutao - Tuvalu	Polynesia	cc by
106793	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Niua Islands, Tonga	Polynesia	cc by
23269	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - St Lucia System, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23273	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Table Mountain National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77932	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Haiti	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
107637	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Huvalu Conservation Area, Niue	Polynesia	cc by
24493	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Liberia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23305	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Lebanon	Western Asia	cc by
29007	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cyprus	Western Asia	cc by
28959	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Nauru	Micronesia	cc by
55695	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bikar Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23278	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Marakele National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
31955	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Saint Lucia	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
106370	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ha'apai group, Tonga	Polynesia	cc by
55687	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bokak Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
77919	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Sweden	Northern Europe	cc by
24523	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Slovenia	Southern Europe	cc by
24472	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Namibia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23199	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tanganyika, Zambia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by

23328	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Saint Martin (French part)	-	cc by
77933	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mozambique	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28938	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Little Cayman, Cayman Islands	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
28949	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Svalbard, Norway	Northern Europe	cc by
28916	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - La Palma, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
28998	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23285	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands		cc by
24511	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - South Sudan		cc by
24530	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Rwanda	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24504	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bermuda	Northern America	cc by
31965	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Soqatra, Yemen	Western Asia	cc by
28951	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - French Southern and Antarctic Lands Terres australes et antarctiques françaises (TAAF), France	Western Europe	cc by
26137	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Argentina	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
31950	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Egypt	Northern Africa	cc by
29120	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Burundi	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
29004	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Pohnpei, Federated States of Micronesia	-	cc by
23239	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Matenga Nature Reserve, Eswatini	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55641	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Utirik Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
31951	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Saudi Arabia	Western Asia	cc by
23288	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Virgin Islands, British	-	cc by
24515	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Libya	Northern Africa	cc by
24520	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Indonesia	South-eastern Asia	cc by

28941	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cayman Islands	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23372	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cosmoledo, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55690	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Erikub Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
55689	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Jabat Island, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
28965	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tokelau	Polynesia	cc by
77927	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Reunion	-	cc by
24481	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Djibouti	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28910	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Hungary	Eastern Europe	cc by
20359	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Hawaii, United States (ver.2.0, 2022)	-	cc0
105526	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tongatapu Island, Tonga	Polynesia	cc by
23364	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Curieuse Special Reserve, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
108059	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Atoll Nui, Tuvalu	Polynesia	cc by
23236	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Amani Forest Nature Reserve, Tanzania	-	cc by
28813	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Greece	Southern Europe	cc by
55692	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ebon Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23247	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Rapa Nui (Isla de Pascua, Easter Island)	South America	cc by
23266	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Verloren Valei Nature Reserve, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
30075	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Pitcairn Islands- Great Britain	Polynesia	cc by
28816	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mwali (Mohéli), Comoros	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24474	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Georgia	Western Asia	cc by
31927	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Nepal	Southern Asia	cc by
106369	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Vava'u group, Tonga	Polynesia	cc by
23302	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Falkland Islands (Islas Malvinas)	-	cc by
55870	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ailinginae Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
28953	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kiribati	Micronesia	cc by
31961	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tunisia	Northern Africa	cc by
28907	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - France	Western Europe	cc by

55694	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bikini Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23356	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Morne-Seychellois National Park, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77931	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Guatemala	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
24519	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - India	Southern Asia	cc by
28955	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
31964	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Myanmar	South-eastern Asia	cc by
23370	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cousin Special Reserve, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23226	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Serengeti - Mara Ecosystem (Kenya, Tanzania)	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23274	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Richtersveld National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23275	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Namaqua National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77947	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Peru	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23347	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Vallée de Mai Nature Reserve, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23247	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Rapa Nui (Isla de Pascua, Easter Island)	-	cc by
28915	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - La Gomera, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
108059	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Atoll Nui, Tuvalu	Polynesia	cc by
23190	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Lake Mburo, Uganda	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28937	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cambodia	South-eastern Asia	cc by
31945	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Yemen	Western Asia	cc by
55651	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mejit Island, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
55654	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Lae Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
55692	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ebon Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23228	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Serengeti National Park, Tanzania	-	cc by
23332	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mauritania	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
108058	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Atoll Nukulaelae, Tuvalu	Polynesia	cc by

28913	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tenerife, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
23284	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Saint Helena, Saint Helena, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23306	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Turkmenistan	Central Asia	cc by
106369	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Vava'u group, Tonga	Polynesia	cc by
24482	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Niger	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
31956	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Chile	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23280	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bulgaria	Eastern Europe	cc by
23356	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Morne-Seychellois National Park, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23365	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cousine Island, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23276	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Mountain Zebra National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24496	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Sao Tome and Principe	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
27905	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Wallis and Futuna	Polynesia	cc by
28929	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kyrgyzstan	Central Asia	cc by
25062	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Qatar	Western Asia	cc by
23327	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - French Polynesia	Polynesia	cc by
24473	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Montenegro	Southern Europe	cc by
107419	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Protected areas, Tonga	Polynesia	cc by
77942	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Republic of Korea	-	cc by
24503	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Dominica	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
77953	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bahamas	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
24524	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Estonia	Northern Europe	cc by
23281	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – British Antarctic Territory, Antarctica		cc by
23296	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Augrabies Falls National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by

55696	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Aur Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
28945	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Colombia	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
77920	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Iceland	Northern Europe	cc by
28933	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Chad	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24533	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Maldives	Southern Asia	cc by
25061	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Malawi	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23227	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Serengeti - Ngorongoro Biosphere Reserve, Tanzania	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55646	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Rongdik Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
55648	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Namdik Atoll Ramsar site, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23240	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Malalotja Nature Reserve, Eswatini	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
55652	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Maloelap Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23374	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Aldabra Atoll, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24510	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Turkey	-	cc by
55647	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Namu Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
24498	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - China	Eastern Asia	cc by
28912	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Fuerteventura, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
24486	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Zambia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23290	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Karoo National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23361	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Islets of Farquhar Atoll, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
30412	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Afghanistan	Southern Asia	cc by
24531	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tanzania	-	cc by
77957	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Laos	-	cc by
24525	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Liechtenstein	Western Europe	cc by
24488	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Gambia	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
24475	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Iran	-	cc by
24499	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Papua New Guinea		cc by

29121	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Andorra	Southern Europe	cc by
55645	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Rongelap Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
24497	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Finland	Northern Europe	cc by
28942	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Iraq	Western Asia	cc by
23441	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Moldova	-	cc by
24501	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Benin	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
31960	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
77946	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Trinidad and Tobago	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23291	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kalahari Gemsbok National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
23287	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Turks and Caicos Islands	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
31952	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ireland	Northern Europe	cc by
77956	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Grenada	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23245	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Lord Howe Island, Australia	Australia and New Zealand	cc by
55653	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Majuro Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23298	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Addo-Elephant National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
25060	GRIIS Checklist of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bosnia and Herzegovina	Southern Europe	cc by
24534	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Malta	Southern Europe	cc by
28906	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - New Caledonia, France		cc by
23302	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species – Falkland Islands (Islas Malvinas)	-	cc by
24478	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Albania	Southern Europe	cc by
28804	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - French Southern and Antarctic Territories (TAAF), Scattered Islands - Îles Éparses, France	Western Europe	cc by
77958	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kuwait	Western Asia	cc by

28911	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Gran Canaria, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
55639	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Wotje Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23271	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - West Coast National Park, South Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28955	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
77922	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Dominican Republic	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
23359	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ile-aux-Vaches Nature Reserve, Seychelles	Sub-Saharan Africa	cc by
28805	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Singapore	South-eastern Asia	cc by
22855	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Greenland	Northern America	cc by
55656	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kili Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
55698	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ailuk Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
28953	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Kiribati	Micronesia	cc by
55726	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Ailinglaplap Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
77944	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Nicaragua	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
77931	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Guatemala	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
55640	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Wotho Atoll, Marshall Islands	Micronesia	cc by
23236	Protected Areas - Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Amani Forest Nature Reserve, Tanzania	-	cc by
28813	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Greece	Southern Europe	cc by
77940	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tajikistan	Central Asia	cc by
77948	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Belize	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
28917	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - El Hierro, Islas Canarias, Spain	Southern Europe	cc by
24480	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Costa Rica	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
31961	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Tunisia	Northern Africa	cc by

31927	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Nepal	Southern Asia	cc by
3310	Lista de especies de plantas exóticas y trasplantadas de Colombia	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by nc
30530	Información bioecológica de flora exótica con potencial invasor en Colombia	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by nc
30529	Especies de fauna invasora en el territorio continental e insular colombiano	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by nc
9501	Lista de especies florísticas invasoras e introducidas en los departamentos Chocó y Valle del Cauca - 2012	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by nc
53124	A preliminary taxon name list for "Freshwater Invasive Species in Europe. A project of the GBIF Nodes of Europe"	Southern Europe	cc by
36442	Alien Flora of Turkey	Western Asia	cc by
301869	Alien flora of the Mediterranean Lesvos Island (East Aegean, Greece)	Southern Europe	cc by nc
23967	Global database of alien macrofungi	Southern Europe	cc by
50982	<i>Ctenosciara alexanderkoenigi</i> sp. n. (Diptera: Sciaridae), an exotic invader in Germany?	Western Europe	cc by
284161	Taxonomic review of the genus <i>Nycteola</i> Hübner (Lepidoptera, Nolidae) from Korea including potential invasive pests	-	cc by
58508	Freshwater fishes (Actinopterygii) of Kenyir Reservoir, Peninsular Malaysia: Updated checklist, taxonomic concerns and alien species	South-eastern Asia	cc by
52003	First description of the male caste of the Himalayan endemic ant <i>Lasius alienoflavus</i> Bingham, 1903 (Hymenoptera: Formicidae), with re-description of the female and queen castes	-	cc by
292348	First record of the hippolytid shrimp <i>Hippolyte australiensis</i> (Stimpson, 1860) (Crustacea, Decapoda) from China	Eastern Asia	cc by
174665	New species and new records of exotic Scolytinae (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) in Europe	-	cc by
5131	<i>Brachymna tenuis</i> Stål, 1861 (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae), a new invasive bamboo pest in Korea with notes on insects associated with bamboos	-	cc by
52070	New records in vascular plants alien to Kyrgyzstan	Central Asia	cc by
56520	<i>Drechslerella daliensis</i> and <i>D. xiaguanensis</i> (Orbiliales, Orbiliaceae), two new nematode-trapping fungi from Yunnan, China	Eastern Asia	cc by
51985	The Afrotropical <i>Miomantis caffra</i> Saussure 1871 and <i>M. paykullii</i> Stal 1871: first records of alien mantid species in Portugal and Europe, with an updated checklist of Mantodea in Portugal (Insecta: Mantodea)	Southern Europe	cc by
58508	Freshwater fishes (Actinopterygii) of Kenyir Reservoir, Peninsular Malaysia: Updated checklist, taxonomic concerns and alien species	South-eastern Asia	cc by

30073	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Palau	Micronesia	cc by
77950	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Sudan	Northern Africa	cc by
32110	Manual of the Alien Plants of Belgium	Western Europe	cc0
28552	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Belgium	Western Europe	cc by
7033	Checklist of alien species in the Scheldt estuary in Flanders, Belgium	Western Europe	cc0
31948	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cuba	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
289975	Cadastre of invasive plant species of the Altai krai	-	cc by nc
30389	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Saba, Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
30408	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Curacao, Netherlands	-	cc by
31946	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Cook Islands	Polynesia	cc by
30384	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Aruba	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
30387	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Sint Maarten, Netherlands	-	cc by
30872	Inventory of alien macroinvertebrates in Flanders, Belgium	Western Europe	cc0
30409	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Bonaire, Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
25573	Checklist of alien birds of Belgium	Western Europe	cc0
31946	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species- Cook Islands	Polynesia	cc by
30384	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Aruba	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by
31948	Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species - Cuba	Latin America and the Caribbean	cc by

Annex 3

The ChecklistBank habitats list comprises 4,366 taxon names (3,110 unique) associated with 228 of the 233 habitat types defined under the Habitats Directive. Five habitat types have no characteristic species listed.

ID	habitatName	genus	species	subspecies
1110	Sandbanks which are slightly covered by sea water all the time	10	24	0
1120	Posidonia beds (<i>Posidonia oceanica</i>)	0	6	0
1130	Estuaries	4	6	0
1150	Coastal lagoons	11	18	0
1160	Large shallow inlets and bays	2	3	0
1170	Reefs	16	25	0
1180	Submarine structures made by leaking gases	0	2	0
1210	Annual vegetation of drift lines	2	23	0
1220	Perennial vegetation of stony banks	0	10	0
1230	Vegetated sea cliffs of the Atlantic and Baltic coasts	3	29	2
1240	Vegetated sea cliffs of the Mediterranean coasts with endemic <i>Limonium</i> spp.	4	5	0
1250	Vegetated sea cliffs with endemic flora of the Macaronesian coasts	2	18	1
1310	<i>Salicornia</i> and other annuals colonising mud and sand	5	28	0
1320	<i>Spartina</i> swards (<i>Spartinion maritimae</i>)	1	3	0
1330	Atlantic salt meadows (<i>Glauco-Puccinellietalia maritimae</i>)	1	30	0
1340	Inland salt meadows	1	15	0
1410	Mediterranean salt meadows (<i>Juncetalia maritimi</i>)	0	41	0
1420	Mediterranean and thermo-Atlantic halophilous scrubs (<i>Sarcocornetea fruticosi</i>)	3	27	0
1430	Halo-nitrophilous scrubs (<i>Pegano-Salsoletea</i>)	0	12	0
1510	Mediterranean salt steppes (<i>Limonietalia</i>)	1	7	0
1520	Iberian gypsum steppes (<i>Gypsophiletalia</i>)	0	9	0
1530	Pannonic salt steppes and salt marshes	0	56	1
1610	Baltic esker islands with sandy, rocky and shingle beach vegetation and sublittoral vegetation	0	24	0
1620	Boreal baltic islets and small islands	0	27	2
1630	Boreal baltic coastal meadows	0	36	1
1640	Boreal Baltic sandy beaches with perennial vegetation	0	19	2
1650	Boreal Baltic narrow inlets	0	25	0
2110	Embryonic shifting dunes	0	13	1
2120	Shifting dunes along the shoreline with <i>Ammophila</i>	0	17	0
2130	Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation (grey dunes)	5	36	2

2140	Decalcified fixed dunes with <i>Empetrum nigrum</i>	0	7	1
2150	Atlantic decalcified fixed dunes (<i>Calluno-Ulicetea</i>)	1	12	0
2160	Dunes with <i>Hippophae rhamnoides</i>	0	1	0
2170	Dunes with <i>Salix repens</i> ssp. <i>argentea</i> (<i>Salicion arenariae</i>)	0	12	1
2180	Wooded dunes of the Atlantic Continental and Boreal region	2	11	0
2190	Humid dune slacks	0	9	0
21A0	Machairs	1	7	1
2210	<i>Crucianellion maritimae</i> fixed beach dunes	0	2	0
2220	Dunes with <i>Euphorbia terracina</i>	0	4	0
2230	<i>Malcolmietalia</i> dune grasslands	0	6	0
2240	<i>Brachypodietalia</i> dune grasslands with annuals	1	0	0
2250	Coastal dunes with <i>Juniperus</i>	0	8	2
2270	Wooded dunes with <i>Pinus pinea</i> and/or <i>Pinus pinaster</i>	0	4	1
2310	Dry sand heaths with <i>Calluna</i> and <i>Genista</i>	0	3	0
2320	Dry sand heaths with <i>Calluna</i> and <i>Empetrum nigrum</i>	0	3	0
2330	Inland dunes with open <i>Corynephorus</i> and <i>Agrostis</i>	3	7	0
2340	Pannonic inland dunes	0	10	2
3110	Oligotrophic waters containing very few minerals of sandy plains (<i>Littorelletalia uniflorae</i>)	3	12	0
3120	Oligotrophic waters containing very few minerals generally on sandy soils of the West Mediterranean with <i>Isoetes</i> spp.	1	15	0
3130	Oligotrophic to mesotrophic standing waters with vegetation of the <i>Littorelletea uniflorae</i> and/or <i>Isoeto- Nanojuncetea</i>	1	25	1
3140	Hard oligo-mesotrophic waters with benthic vegetation of <i>Chara</i> spp.	2	2	0
3150	Natural eutrophic lakes with <i>Magnopotamion</i> or <i>Hydrocharition</i> -type vegetation	6	11	0
3160	Natural dystrophic lakes and ponds	3	10	0
3170	Mediterranean temporary ponds	0	51	0
3180	Turloughs	0	8	0
3190	Lakes of gypsum karst	0	9	0
31A0	Transylvanian hot-spring lotus beds	0	8	0
3210	Fennoscandian natural rivers	2	19	2
3220	Alpine rivers and the herbaceous vegetation along their banks	0	37	1
3230	Alpine rivers and their ligneous vegetation with	0	4	1
3240	Alpine rivers and their ligneous vegetation with <i>Salix elaeagnos</i>	3	4	1
3250	Constantly flowing Mediterranean rivers with	0	4	0
3260	Water courses of plain to montane levels with the <i>Ranunculion fluitantis</i> and <i>Callitricho-Batrachion</i> vegetation	3	12	2
3270	Rivers with muddy banks with <i>Chenopodium rubri</i> p.p. and <i>Bidention</i> p.p. vegetation	1	4	0

3280	Constantly flowing Mediterranean rivers with Paspalo- Agrostidion species and hanging curtains of Salix and Populus alba	1	6	0
3290	Intermittently flowing Mediterranean rivers of the Paspalo-Agrostidion	0	5	0
32A0	Tufa cascades of karstic rivers of the Dinaric Alps	0	18	0
4010	Northern Atlantic wet heaths with Erica tetralix	0	6	0
4020	Temperate Atlantic wet heaths with Erica ciliaris and	1	11	0
4030	European dry heaths	1	28	0
4040	Dry Atlantic coastal heaths with Erica vagans	0	2	0
4050	Endemic macaronesian heaths	0	20	2
4060	Alpine and Boreal heaths	2	49	0
4070	Bushes with Pinus mugo and Rhododendron hirsutum	1	8	0
4080	Sub-Arctic Salix spp. scrub	1	8	0
4090	Endemic oro-Mediterranean heaths with gorse	9	63	17
40A0	Subcontinental peri-Pannonic scrub	0	56	0
40B0	Rhodope Potentilla fruticosa thickets	0	11	0
40C0	Ponto-Sarmatic deciduous thickets	1	25	0
5110	Stable xerothermophilous formations with Buxus sempervirens on rock slopes (Berberidion p.p.)	1	14	0
5120	Mountain Cytisus purgans formations	0	1	0
5130	Juniperus communis formations on heaths or calcareous grasslands	2	12	1
5140	Cistus palhinhae formations on maritime wet heaths	0	6	2
5210	Arborescent matorral with Juniperus spp.	1	7	0
5220	Arborescent matorral with Zyziphus	0	8	4
5230	Arborescent matorral with Laurus nobilis	0	14	1
5310	Laurus nobilis thickets	0	1	0
5320	Low formations of Euphorbia close to cliffs	0	7	1
5330	Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-desert scrub	3	22	5
5410	West Mediterranean clifftop phrygas (Astragalo- Plantagnetum subulatae)	0	6	0
5420	Sarcopoterium spinosum phrygas	0	29	2
5430	Endemic phrygas of the Euphorbio-Verbascion	0	20	2
6110	Rupicolous calcareous or basophilic grasslands of the Alysso-Sedion albi	5	11	0
6120	Xeric sand calcareous grasslands	0	15	1
6130	Calaminarian grasslands of the Violetalia calaminariae	0	8	0
6140	Siliceous Pyrenean Festuca eskia grasslands	0	9	0
6150	Siliceous alpine and boreal grasslands	0	11	0
6160	Oro-Iberian Festuca indigesta grasslands	0	1	0
6170	Alpine and subalpine calcareous grasslands	0	68	7

6180	Macaronesian mesophile grasslands	1	14	0
6190	Rupicolous pannonic grasslands (Stipo-Festucetalia pallentis)	0	27	0
6210	Semi-natural dry grasslands and scrubland facies on calcareous substrates(Festuco-Brometalia)	3	59	1
6220	Pseudo-steppe with grasses and annuals of the Thero-Brachypodietea	0	2	0
6230	Species-rich Nardus grasslands, on siliceous	0	29	0
6240	Sub-pannonic steppic grasslands	0	36	1
6250	Pannonic loess steppic grasslands	0	19	0
6260	Pannonic sand steppes	0	24	3
6270	Fennoscandian lowland species-rich dry to mesic grasslands	6	23	0
6280	Nordic alvar and precambrian calcareous flatrocks	2	32	1
62A0	Eastern sub-mediterranean dry grasslands (Scorzoneratalia villosae)	0	18	1
62B0	Serpentinophilous grasslands of Cyprus	0	14	3
62C0	Ponto-Sarmatic steppes	0	37	1
62D0	Oro-Moesian acidophilous grasslands	0	14	0
6310	Dehesas with evergreen Quercus	0	7	0
6410	Molinia meadows on calcareous, peaty or clayey-silt- laden soils (Molinion caeruleae)	0	35	0
6420	Mediterranean tall humid herb grasslands of the	0	40	1
6430	Hydrophilous tall herb fringe communities of plains and of the montane to alpine levels	0	34	0
6440	Alluvial meadows of river valleys of the Cnidion dubii	0	9	0
6450	Northern boreal alluvial meadows	0	18	1
6460	Peat grasslands of Troodos	0	17	0
6510	Lowland hay meadows (Alopecurus pratensis, Sanguisorba officinalis)	0	20	1
6520	Mountain hay meadows	1	35	1
6530	Fennoscandian wooded meadows	2	27	0
6540	Sub-Mediterranean grasslands of the Molinio-Hordeion secalini	0	14	0
7110	Active raised bogs	1	50	0
7130	Blanket bogs (if active bog)	1	36	0
7140	Transition mires and quaking bogs	1	36	0
7150	Depressions on peat substrates of the Rhynchosporion	0	5	0
7160	Fennoscandian mineral-rich springs and springfens	4	31	0
7210	Calcareous fens with Cladium mariscus and species of the Caricion davallianae	0	15	0
7220	Petrifying springs with tufa formation (Cratoneurion)	0	19	0
7230	Alkaline fens	1	34	1
7240	Alpine pioneer formations of Caricion bicoloris-atrofuscae	2	16	0
7310	Aapa mires	1	36	0

7320	Palsa mires	3	7	1
8110	Siliceous scree of the montane to snow levels (Androsacetalia alpinae and Galeopsetalia ladani)	0	26	3
8120	Calcareous and calcshist screes of the montane to alpine levels (Thlaspietea rotundifolii)	0	33	2
8130	Western Mediterranean and thermophilous scree	0	59	5
8140	Eastern Mediterranean screes	0	13	1
8150	Medio-European upland siliceous screes	0	5	0
8160	Medio-European calcareous scree of hill and montane levels	0	6	0
8210	Calcareous rocky slopes with chasmophytic vegetation	0	71	7
8220	Siliceous rocky slopes with chasmophytic vegetation	0	52	5
8230	Siliceous rock with pioneer vegetation of the Sedo- Scleranthion or of the Sedo albi-Veronicion dillenii	1	21	0
8240	Limestone pavements	3	29	1
8310	Caves not open to the public	4	3	0
8320	Fields of lava and natural excavations	1	5	0
9010	Western Taiga	3	41	0
9020	Fennoscandian hemiboreal natural old broad-leaved deciduous forests (Quercus, Tilia, Acer, Fraxinus or Ulmus) rich in epiphytes	3	30	0
9030	Natural forests of primary succession stages of landupheaval coast	0	5	0
9040	Nordic subalpine/subarctic forests with Betula pubescens ssp. czerepanovii	2	16	1
9050	Fennoscandian herb-rich forests with Picea abies	3	22	0
9060	Coniferous forests on, or connected to, glaciofluvial eskers	0	25	3
9070	Fennoscandian wooded pastures	3	19	0
9080	Fennoscandian deciduous swamp woods	0	31	0
9110	Luzulo-Fagetum beech forests	0	11	0
9120	Atlantic acidophilous beech forests with Ilex and sometimes also Taxus in the shrublayer (Quercinion robori-petraeae or Ilici-Fagenion)	2	14	0
9130	Asperulo-Fagetum beech forests	2	20	0
9140	Medio-European subalpine beech woods with Acer and Rumex arifolius	0	4	0
9150	Medio-European limestone beech forests of the Cephalanthero-Fagion	1	24	2
9160	Sub-Atlantic and medio-European oak or oak- hornbeam forests of the Carpinion betuli	0	16	0
9170	Galio-Carpinetum oak-hornbeam forests	0	14	0
9180	Tilio-Acerion forests of slopes, screes and ravines	3	63	0
9190	Old acidophilous oak woods with Quercus robur on sandy plains	1	32	0
91A0	Old sessile oak woods with Ilex and Blechnum in the British Isles	2	8	0
91AA	Eastern white oak woods	1	10	0
91B0	Thermophilous Fraxinus angustifolia woods	0	3	0

91BA	Moesian silver fir forests	0	5	0
91C0	Caledonian forest	2	19	1
91CA	Rhodopide and Balkan Range Scots pine forests	0	14	0
91D0	Bog woodland	3	24	0
9,1E+0 1	Alluvial forests with <i>Alnus glutinosa</i> and <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	5	32	0
91F0	Riparian mixed forests of <i>Quercus robur</i> <i>Ulmus laevis</i> and <i>Ulmus minor</i> <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> or <i>Fraxinus angustifolia</i>	0	19	1
91G0	Pannonic woods with <i>Quercus petraea</i> and <i>Carpinus betulus</i>	0	29	0
91H0	Pannonian woods with <i>Quercus pubescens</i>	0	37	1
91I0	Euro-Siberian steppic woods with <i>Quercus</i> spp.	1	30	1
91J0	<i>Taxus baccata</i> woods of the British Isles	0	5	0
91K0	Illyrian <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> forests (Aremonio-Fagion)	1	36	1
91L0	Illyrian oak-hornbeam forests (Erythronio-Carpinion)	0	26	2
91M0	Pannonian-Balkan turkey oak-sessile oak forests	0	54	1
91N0	Pannonic inland sand dune thicket (<i>Junipero</i> - <i>Populetum albae</i>)	1	23	0
91P0	Holy Cross fir forests (<i>Abietetum polonicum</i>)	0	25	0
91Q0	Western Carpathian calcicolous <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> forests	0	20	5
91R0	Dinaric dolomite Scots pine forests	0	16	1
91S0	Western Pontic beech forests	0	16	1
91T0	Central European lichen Scots pine forests	0	6	0
91U0	Sarmatic steppe pine forests	0	11	0
91V0	Dacian Beech forests (<i>Symphyto</i> -Fagion)	0	18	2
91W0	Moesian beech forests	0	25	0
91X0	Dobrogean Beech forests	0	19	0
91Y0	Dacian oak & hornbeam forests	0	24	0
91Z0	Moesian Silver lime woods	0	11	0
9210	Apennine beech forests with <i>Taxus</i> and <i>Ilex</i>	0	10	0
9220	Apennine beech forests with <i>Abies alba</i> and beech forests with <i>Abies nebrodensis</i>	0	7	0
9230	Galicio-Portuguese oak woods with <i>Quercus robur</i> and <i>Quercus pyrenaica</i>	0	10	0
9240	<i>Quercus faginea</i> and <i>Quercus canariensis</i> Iberian woods	0	3	0
9250	<i>Quercus trojana</i> woods	1	3	0
9260	<i>Castanea sativa</i> woods	0	1	0
9270	Hellenic beech forests with <i>Abies borisii-regis</i>	0	6	0
9280	<i>Quercus frainetto</i> woods	0	3	0
9290	<i>Cupressus</i> forests	0	3	0
92A0	<i>Salix alba</i> and <i>Populus alba</i> galleries	6	11	0

92B0	Riparian formations on intermittent Mediterranean water courses with <i>Rhododendron ponticum</i>	1	11	3
92C0	<i>Platanus orientalis</i> and <i>Liquidambar orientalis</i> woods	2	40	2
92D0	Southern riparian galleries and thickets	1	7	0
9310	Aegean <i>Quercus brachyphylla</i> forests	0	3	0
9320	<i>Olea</i> and <i>Ceratonia</i> forests	0	4	2
9330	<i>Quercus suber</i> forests	0	4	0
9340	<i>Quercus ilex</i> and <i>Quercus rotundifolia</i> forests	1	12	0
9350	<i>Quercus macrolepis</i> forests	0	1	0
9360	Macaronesian laurel forests	11	57	7
9370	Palm groves of Phoenix	0	3	0
9380	Forests of <i>Ilex aquifolium</i>	2	2	0
9390	Scrub and low forest vegetation with <i>Quercus alnifolia</i>	0	6	0
93A0	Woodlands with <i>Quercus infectoria</i>	0	24	2
9410	Acidophilous <i>Picea</i> forests of the montane to alpine levels	1	2	0
9420	Alpine <i>Larix decidua</i> and/or <i>Pinus cembra</i> forests	0	12	0
9430	Subalpine and montane <i>Pinus uncinata</i> forests (if on gypsum or limestone)	1	27	0
9510	Southern Apennine <i>Abies alba</i> forests	0	1	0
9520	<i>Abies pinsapo</i> forests	0	1	0
9530	(Sub-)Mediterranean pine forests with endemic black pines	0	5	1
9540	Mediterranean pine forests with endemic Mesogean pines	0	25	2
9550	Canarian endemic pine forests	1	23	3
9560	Endemic forests with <i>Juniperus</i> spp.	1	19	1
9570	<i>Tetraclinis articulata</i> forests	0	12	0
9580	Mediterranean <i>Taxus baccata</i> woods	0	5	0
9590	<i>Cedrus brevifolia</i> forests	0	7	0
95A0	High oro-Mediterranean pine forests	0	14	0

